

Supplementary Material

Well-Tempered MCMC simulations for population pharmacokinetic models

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Supplementary Pseudo-code of the tempered MCMC sampler.

```
DoMarkov() {
  Initialize the thetas by sampling from the prior;
  Calculate prior and likelihood;
  Set the perk scale and the pseudo-priors automatically:
  InitPerks();
  CZero = NZero = 100;
  for (iter in 1:nIter) {
    SampleThetasTempered();
    Robbins-Monro updating of the pseudo prior:
    for (i in 0:nPerks) {
      if (i = indexT)
        lnPi[i] = lnPi[i] - CZero / (iter + NZero);
      else
        lnPi[i] = lnPi[i] + CZero / ((iter + NZero) nPerks);
    }
    Sample a new temperature and make it the current one:
    indexT = SamplePerk();
  }
}

InitPerks() {
  Start at perk 1 and just below it:
  MaxNperks = 50; // maximum number of perks
  startT = MaxNperks - 2;
  endT = MaxNperks - 1;
  Perks[startT] = 0.99;
  Perks[endT] = 1.00; // cold perk
  RunLength = 100; // number of MCMC iterations in a block or runs
  Boundary = 0.0; // lowest possible perk
  Loop over running a block, checking results, and adjusting:
  do {
    Set the index of the current perk:
    indexT = startT;
    Run a batch of tempered MCMC simulations:
    RunTemperingBlock();
    Check transition rates in the block:
    CheckTransitions();
    if (the lowest perk is reached) Exit function;
    if (the lowest perk is not reached) {
      Set the pseudo-prior of lowest index to the average of its current
      value and a value obtained by linear extrapolation linearly between
      the pseudo-prior of lowest index and the one just above:
      lnPi[startT] = (lnPi[startT] + Extrapolated) / 2;
      if (the acceptance rate is too low) {
        Go back up half way to the point above:
        Perks[startT] = (Perks[startT] + Perks[startT+1]) / 2;
      }
    }
    if (acceptance rate is OK) {
      if (we have not exceeded the maximum number of perks) {
        The pseudo-priors should be about right, we try to take some
        perks off the grid by examining recursively triplets A, B, C of
        perks and pseudo-priors, removing perk B if the three
        pseudo-priors are aligned (slopes from A to B equal to slope
        from B to C):
        int i = endT;
        int j = i - 2;
        while (j >= startT) {
          if (EqualSlopes()) {
            Remove point i - 1 from the scale, repack the grid
            by copying perks, pseudo-prior, and counts from positions start
            to (i - 2) to positions (start + 1) to (i - 1)
            and setting start to (start + 1). Start is moved up:
            for (k in j:startT) {
              Perks[k+1] = Perks[k];
              lnPi [k+1] = lnPi [k];
              Count[k+1] = Count[k];
            }
            startT = startT + 1;
            if (indexT <= j) indexT = indexT + 1;
            lRunLength = lRunLength - 100; // decrease run length
          }
        }
      }
    }
  }
}
```

```

    }
    else { // slopes are not equal, move i and j down
        i = i - 1;
        j = j - 1;
    }
}
Add a new perk, set it as current perk, and set its value
to the element just inferior to the old one in a preset table:
startT = startT - 1;
indexT = startT;
Perks[startT] = NextDown(Perks[startT+1]);
The pseudo-prior of new perk is set to an average of above and
extrapolated:
lnPi[startT] = (lnPi[startT+1] + Extrapolated) / 2;
Increase run length:
lRunLength = lRunLength + 100;
}
if (we are at the maximum number of perks) Exit function;
}
Re-initialize counts at zero;
}
} while (lowest perk not reached );
}

RunTemperingBlock() {
Run a block of MCMC simulations to adjust the perk scale and pseudo-priors:
for (i in 0:RunLength) {
Sample parameters:
SampleThetasTempered();
Robbins-Munro updating of the pseudo-priors:
for (j in startT:endT) {
if (j = indexT)
logPi[j] -= dCZero / (i + dNZero);
else
logPi[j] += dTmpdCZero / ((i + dNZero) * nPerks);
}
Test the temperature and change indexT accordingly:
indexT = SamplePerk();
}
}

CheckTransitions() {
Check whether the first perk transition rate is between reasonable bounds
and that enough attempts have been made:
if (TransAttempts[startT] < 10)
return (too low)
else
AcceptRate = TransitionsAccepted[startT] / TransitionsAttempted[startT];
if (AcceptRate < 0.30)
return (too low)
else
return (OK)
}

NextDown(Perk) {
Return the element just inferior to the argument in the following table:
Table = {0, 1E-6, 1E-5, 1E-4, 1E-3, 1E-2,
0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8, 0.9,
0.95, 0.97, 0.99, 0.999, 0.9999, 0.99999, 1};
i = 0;
while (Perk > Table[i]) i = i + 1;
if (i = 0)
return (Table[i]);
else
return (Table[i-1]);
}
}

```

```

SampleThetasTempered() {
  Loop over: parameters:
  for (n in 0:nParam) {
    Compute prior and likelihood;
    Save the parameter current value;
    Sample a new value:
    if (perks is not zero) {
      Scale temporarily the jump kernel SD according to current perk
      using the variance of the powered standard normal:
      KernelSD = KernelSD * exp((1 - Perks[indexT]) * Log2PI * 0.25 -
        0.75 * log(Perks[indexT]));
      Sample a new parameter value from the kernel, centered at the old value;
    }
    else
      Perk is zero, sample uniformly or from the prior for IT;
    Recompute prior and likelihood;
    Test the importance ratio and reject or accept;
    if (TestImportanceRatioTempered() = reject)
      Restore parameter value;
    if (TestImportanceRatioTempered() = accept)
      Nothing to do, except for bookkeeping;
  }
}

TestImportanceRatioTempered() {
  if (Perks[indexT] = 0) // always accept jumps at perk zero
    return (accept);
  if (posterior is tempered)
    Pjump = Perks[indexT] *
      (LogPriorNew - LogPrior + LogLikelihoodNew - LogLikelihood) +
      LogKernel - LogKernelNew;
  if (likelihood is tempered)
    Pjump = LogPriorNew - LogPrior +
      Perks[indexT] * (LogLikelihoodNew - LogLikelihood) +
      LogKernel - LogKernelNew;
  Draw a uniform [0,1] variate and compare it to Pjump:
  if (UniformRandom() <= exp(Pjump)) return (accept);
  else return (reject)
}

SamplePerk() {
  Propose a new perk:
  if (indexT = 0) indexT_new = 1;
  else
    if (indexT = nPerks - 1) indexT_new = indexT - 1;
    else
      if (UniformRandom() > 0.5)
        indexT_new = indexT + 1;
      else
        indexT_new = indexT - 1;
  Test the proposed perk:
  if (TestPerk() = accept) return (indexT_new);
  else return (indexT);
}

TestPerk() {
  Test temperature against a uniform [0,1] random number:
  if (the posterior is tempered)
    Pjump = (Perks[indexT_new] - Perks[indexT]) * (LogPrior + LogLikelihood) +
      logPi[indexT_new] - logPi[indexT];
  if (only the likelihood is tempered) // the prior cancels out
    Pjump = (Perks[indexT_new] - Perks[indexT]) * LogLikelihood +
      logPi[indexT_new] - logPi[indexT];
  Correct for edge effects:
  if (indexT_new is at an edge of the perk grid)
    Pjump = Pjump - log(2);
  if (indexT is at an edge of the perk grid)
    Pjump = Pjump + log(2);
  if (UniformRandom() <= exp(Pjump)) return (accept);
  else return (reject)
}

```

Supplementary Table S1. Data for the multi-modal linear regression test case.

(x, y)	(x, y)
(1, -0.9935458)	(1, 1.02795205)
(2, -2.0240228)	(2, 2.00450560)
(3, -3.0077687)	(3, 2.98446460)
(4, -4.0067294)	(4, 4.01383614)
(5, -5.0050039)	(5, 5.00603586)
(6, -6.0210604)	(6, 5.99993913)
(7, -7.0150200)	(7, 7.01104916)
(8, -7.9920540)	(8, 7.99542326)
(9, -9.0092760)	(9, 8.99242493)
(10, -9.9964471)	(10, 10.0076993)

Supplementary Table S2. Data for the Gaussian mean test case.

-1.31559	-0.73666	1.20569	-1.73722	-0.30884	-0.76155	0.21518	0.31707	-0.05521	0.19057
0.89541	1.16196	0.10125	0.71446	0.99934	1.78996	-0.20972	0.79051	-0.82736	-0.57746
0.28609	-0.89058	0.33945	-2.03076	0.62369	-0.35001	1.75051	0.64510	-0.86697	-1.58950
2.08225	-1.60079	-0.33201	0.61762	1.00325	-0.76846	-1.58168	-0.33435	-2.15645	0.30864
0.49061	1.62940	1.04681	1.25895	0.79866	0.93647	-0.93496	-1.10015	-0.63399	0.16543
-0.87284	-0.25812	-0.14671	-1.16375	-0.38878	0.11945	0.44588	0.86473	0.87712	-0.12696
-0.10193	-0.32150	0.07070	-0.32103	0.37842	-1.82517	0.86379	-0.52906	-0.86864	0.48054
-1.71530	2.25930	-1.17660	-1.48330	0.04143	1.22078	-0.65970	-0.20954	-1.66506	0.31825
-1.86426	1.31448	-0.92209	0.39659	0.20253	-0.36113	-0.68786	-0.61799	1.11140	0.62264
0.58069	-0.74544	0.81078	1.32838	-0.38599	0.52883	-0.16352	-1.50377	1.30310	-2.03298

Supplementary Table S3. Data for the theophylline population PK test case. The Napierian logarithms of the eight measured plasma concentrations (in microM) are given in columns C_1 to C_8 .

Subject	Regimen ^a	Dose ^b	$\log C_1$	$\log C_2$	$\log C_3$	$\log C_4$	$\log C_5$	$\log C_6$	$\log C_7$	$\log C_8$
M	IR	L	3.471712	3.418603	3.418603	3.261417	3.217932	-	2.937630	-
M	SR	L	1.809165	2.301641	2.589323	2.407002	2.812467	3.261417	3.074831	3.100149
M	SR-R	L	3.645376	3.659765	3.853921	3.615962	3.471712	3.585657	3.522143	3.522143
N	IR	L	3.454321	3.585657	3.687935	3.454321	3.074831	3.074831	2.877005	2.937630
N	SR	L	1.357179	2.355708	2.546764	2.845257	2.743474	2.502312	2.546764	2.669366
N	SR-R	L	3.659765	3.687935	3.755075	3.755075	3.911079	3.830110	3.554404	3.659765
O	IR	L	3.911079	3.381561	3.381561	3.381561	3.172469	2.966617	2.877005	2.669366
O	SR	L	-	2.502312	2.778565	3.022187	3.100149	2.937630	-	-
O	SR-R	L	3.780717	3.985980	4.129768	4.181954	4.181954	3.817989	3.755075	3.645376
P	IR	L	3.362513	3.343095	3.217932	3.124841	3.124841	3.124841	2.877005	2.669366
P	SR	L	1.809165	2.244483	2.407002	2.407002	2.589323	2.743474	2.669366	2.907777
P	SR-R	L	3.418603	3.538404	3.381561	3.538404	3.659765	3.048855	2.812467	2.994788
P	SR-R	H	4.709587	4.729389	4.673960	4.709587	4.626205	4.467515	4.345743	4.223454
Q	IR	L	3.148939	3.124841	2.966617	2.778565	2.630145	2.050327	1.896176	1.809165
Q	SR	L	-	-	1.713854	2.407002	2.589323	2.589323	2.183858	2.301641
Q	SR-R	L	2.743474	2.812467	2.778565	2.630145	2.455792	2.244483	2.244483	2.244483
R	IR	L	2.877005	2.907777	2.877005	2.743474	2.301641	2.050327	1.809165	1.809165
R	SR	L	-	-	2.183858	2.244483	2.301641	2.907777	2.630145	2.778565
R	SR-R	L	3.022187	2.877005	3.148939	3.100149	3.074831	2.707106	2.669366	2.455792
R	SR-R	H	3.659765	3.865617	3.865617	3.817989	3.630777	3.323292	3.522143	3.239911

^a IR: immediate release form; SR: sustained release; SR-R: sustained release up to steady-state. Plasma sampling times for IR and SR were 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 8, 10, and 12 hours. Sampling times for SR-R were 73, 74, 75, 76, 78, 80, 82, and 84 hours.

^b doses level code L: 190 mg (1054.56 micromoles); H: 380 mg (2109.12 micromoles).

^c NA: not available (not measured).

Supplementary Table S4. Summary of the eight human acetaminophen studies used for model calibration.

Study	Dose	Number of subjects	Mean body mass	Reference
1	325 mg	8	68 kg	(Volak et al. 2013)
2	1000 mg	6	68 kg	(Jensen et al. 2004)
3	1000 mg	5	60 kg	(Shinoda et al. 2007)
4	1000 mg	12	70 kg	(Kim et al. 2011)
5	20 mg/kg	8	72 kg	(Prescott 1980)
6	20 mg/kg	6	57 kg	(Chan et al. 1997)
7	20 mg/kg	11	57 kg	(Critchley et al. 1986)
8	79 mg/kg	9	73 kg	(Chiew et al. 2010)

Supplementary Table S5. Data for the Volak *et al.* acetaminophen studies. The Napierian logarithms of the measured plasma concentrations (in micrograms/liter), averaged across subjects, are given. Time is in hours.

Time	Acetaminophen	Acetaminophen-glucuronide	Acetaminophen-sulfate
0.5	7.5756	5.7038	6.5539
1.0	7.8973	7.6639	7.3524
1.5	8.0359	8.1490	7.7098
2.0	7.9409	8.3687	7.7579
2.5	7.7536	8.4680	7.7007
3.0	7.5909	8.5192	7.5909
4.0	7.3395	8.4338	7.4384
6.0	6.6758	8.0520	6.9177
8.0	6.1654	7.5549	6.4489
10	-	7.1624	6.1841

Supplementary Table S6. Data for the Jensen *et al.* acetaminophen studies. The Napierian logarithms of the measured plasma concentrations (in micrograms/liter), averaged across subjects, are given. Time is in hours.

Time	Acetaminophen	Acetaminophen-glucuronide	Acetaminophen-sulfate
0.5	9.2797	8.3935	8.3170
1.0	9.4681	9.3632	8.7968
1.5	9.2923	9.8072	8.9727
2.0	9.0719	9.982	8.8870
3.0	8.7246	10.0493	8.7968
4.0	8.3994	9.9260	8.539
5.0	8.1881	9.7817	8.4138
6.0	7.8920	9.5520	8.1712
8.0	7.3309	9.1014	7.6798
10	-	8.6473	7.2098

Supplementary Table S7. Data for the Shinoda *et al.* acetaminophen studies. The Napierian logarithms of the measured plasma concentrations (in micrograms/liter), averaged across subjects, are given. Time is in hours.

Time	Acetaminophen	Acetaminophen-glucuronide	Acetaminophen-sulfate
0.25	9.6989	7.2842	7.5479
0.50	9.7585	9.1686	8.4928
0.75	9.6486	9.4551	8.5595
1.0	9.5324	9.6247	8.5595
2.0	9.2686	9.9808	8.5884
3.0	9.0372	9.9091	8.4446
4.0	8.8291	9.7584	8.2610
6.0	8.4617	9.3016	7.7043

Supplementary Table S8. Data for the Kim *et al.* acetaminophen studies. The Napierian logarithms of the measured plasma concentrations (in micrograms/liter), averaged across subjects, are given. Time is in hours.

Time	Acetaminophen	Acetaminophen-glucuronide	Acetaminophen-sulfate
0.25	8.3405	6.2383	6.2383
0.50	8.0456	6.9276	6.5482
1.0	8.5271	8.1831	7.6917
1.5	9.0607	8.7749	8.1577
2.0	9.0927	9.1485	8.3939
3.0	9.0466	9.5819	8.5773
4.0	8.8393	9.7050	8.5679
6.0	8.2188	9.5956	8.2242
8.0	7.5704	9.1788	7.7187
10	-	8.6945	7.2226

Supplementary Table S9. Data for the Prescott *et al.* acetaminophen studies. The Napierian logarithms of the measured plasma concentrations (in micrograms/liter), averaged across subjects, are given. Time is in hours.

Time	Acetaminophen	Acetaminophen-glucuronide	Acetaminophen-sulfate
0.25	9.6486	8.07220	8.1743
0.50	9.8363	8.98040	8.8166
0.75	9.8416	9.50470	9.0136
1.0	9.7981	9.80600	9.1653
1.5	9.6550	10.1138	9.1427
2.0	9.5178	10.2139	9.0802
3.0	9.2203	10.1567	8.9097
4.0	8.9187	10.0871	8.8052
6.0	8.2940	9.63040	8.3940
8.0	7.8360	9.24250	7.9587

Supplementary Table S10. Data for the Chan *et al.* acetaminophen studies. The Napierian logarithms of the measured plasma concentrations (in micrograms/liter), averaged across subjects, are given. Time is in hours.

Time	Acetaminophen	Acetaminophen-glucuronide	Acetaminophen-sulfate
0.5	9.9184	8.84960	8.5855
1.0	9.8934	9.63460	8.9833
1.5	9.8092	9.96050	9.1311
2.0	9.6486	10.0689	9.1195
3.0	9.3147	10.0689	8.9737
4.0	9.0131	9.95850	8.8098
5.0	8.7323	9.80120	8.6137
6.0	8.4949	9.65010	8.4609
7.0	8.1719	9.46020	8.2530
8.0	8.0678	9.30750	8.0158

Supplementary Table S11. Data for the Critchley *et al.* acetaminophen studies. The Napierian logarithms of the measured plasma concentrations (in micrograms/liter), averaged across subjects, are given. Time is in hours.

Time	Acetaminophen	Acetaminophen-glucuronide	Acetaminophen-sulfate
0.5	9.9942	8.3168	8.4314
1.0	9.8147	9.4047	8.9362
1.5	9.6291	9.6884	9.0191
2.0	9.4880	9.8343	8.9872
3.0	9.2496	9.8896	8.9158
4.0	8.9708	9.8319	8.7388
5.0	8.6604	9.6924	8.5682
6.0	8.3825	9.5144	8.3765
7.0	8.1970	9.2735	8.2040
8.0	7.9374	9.0257	7.9640
9.0	-	8.8558	7.7515
10	-	8.7345	7.5234

Supplementary Table S12. Data for the Chiew *et al.* acetaminophen studies. The Napierian logarithms of the measured plasma concentrations (in micrograms/liter), averaged across subjects, are given. Time is in hours.

Time	Acetaminophen	Acetaminophen-glucuronide	Acetaminophen-sulfate
0.50	11.1496	9.32880	8.6702
0.75	11.3570	10.1109	9.1882
1.0	11.1583	10.5093	9.3634
1.5	10.9794	11.0057	9.5770
2.0	10.9794	11.2879	9.7297
3.0	10.8735	11.5434	9.8477
4.0	10.6532	11.5929	9.9619
6.0	10.1775	11.4362	9.8872
8.0	9.6145	11.0941	9.6890
10	-	10.7324	9.4287
12	-	10.3191	9.0757

Supplementary Table S13. Summary of prior distributions for the acetaminophen PBPK model parameters.

Parameter	Index	Description	Unit	Distribution	Geometric mean or minimum ^a	SD on log scale ($\pm z$ -score truncation) or maximum ^b
<i>Tg</i>	1	Gastric emptying time constant	h	Log-normal	0.23	0.5 (± 3)
<i>CYP_VmaxC</i>	2	Cytochrome P450 metabolism Vmax	$\mu\text{mole/h/kg}^{0.75}$	Log-uniform	0.14	150
<i>SULT_Km_apap</i>	3	Sulfatation Km	μM	Log-normal	300	1 (± 1)
<i>SULT_VmaxC</i>	4	Sulfation Vmax	$\mu\text{mole/h/kg}^{0.75}$	Log-uniform	1	3.26×10^6
<i>UGT_Km</i>	5	Glucuronidation Km	μM	Log-normal	6.0×10^3	1 (± 1)
<i>UGT_VmaxC</i>	6	Glucuronidation Vmax	$\mu\text{mole/h/kg}^{0.75}$	Log-uniform	1	3.26×10^6
<i>Km_AG</i>	7	APAP-G hepatic transport Km	μM	Log-normal	1.99×10^4	0.3 (± 3)
<i>Vmax_AG</i>	8	APAP-G hepatic transport Vmax	$\mu\text{mole/h}$	Log-uniform	1.09×10^3	3.26×10^6
<i>Km_AS</i>	9	APAP-S hepatic transport Km	μM	Log-normal	2.99×10^4	0.22 (± 3)
<i>Vmax_AS</i>	10	APAP-S hepatic transport Vmax	$\mu\text{mole/h}$	Log-uniform	1.09×10^3	3.26×10^6
<i>kGA_syn</i>	11	UDPGA synthesis rate	1/h	Log-uniform	1	4.43×10^5
<i>kPAPS_syn</i>	12	PAPS synthesis rate	1/h	Log-uniform	1	4.43×10^5
<i>CLC_APAP</i>	13	APAP clearance	$\text{L/h/kg}^{0.75}$	Log-uniform	2.48×10^{-3}	2.718
<i>CLC_AG</i>	14	APAP-G clearance	$\text{L/h/kg}^{0.75}$	Log-uniform	2.48×10^{-3}	2.718
<i>CLC_AS</i>	15	APAP-S clearance	$\text{L/h/kg}^{0.75}$	Log-uniform	2.48×10^{-3}	2.718
<i>QCC</i>	16	Cardiac output	$\text{L/h/kg}^{0.75}$	Log-normal	16.2	0.4 (± 2)
<i>BP_APAP</i>	17	Blood to plasma ratio	–	Log-uniform	0.1	1
<i>PF_APAP</i>	18	APAP fat over blood partition coefficient	–	Log-normal	0.447	0.4 (± 2)
<i>PL_APAP</i>	19	APAP liver over blood partition coefficient	–	Log-normal	0.687	0.4 (± 2)
<i>PM_APAP</i>	20	APAP muscle over blood partition coefficient	–	Log-normal	0.687	0.4 (± 2)

^a Geometric mean if the distribution is log-normal; minimum if uniform.

^b SD on the log scale if the distribution is log-normal (The z -score truncation indicates the number of SDs around the mean, *e.g.* a z -score of 3 means truncation at ± 3 SDs around the mean); maximum if uniform.

Supplementary Text S1. GNU MCSim model for the multi-modal linear regression test case.

```
# Linear Model
# P = A + B * time + Normal (0, SD_true)
# Setting SD_true to zero gives the deterministic version
#-----

# Outputs
Outputs = {y, z};

# Model Parameters
A = 0;
B = 1;
SD_y = 0;
SD_z = 0;

CalcOutputs {
  y = A + B * t;
  z = y;
}

End.
```

Supplementary Text S2. MCSim MCMC script for the multi-modal linear regression test case.

```
# Linear model
#-----
MCMC ("linear2.LTMCMC.out", # output file
      "", # name of restart file
      "", # name of data file
      10000000, 4, # iterations, print predictions flag,
      200, 10000000, # printing frequency, iters to print
      56893.56); # dSeed

Level {

  Distrib(B, Uniform, -10, 10);
  Distrib(SD_y, LogUniform, 0.001, 100);
  Distrib(SD_z, LogUniform, 0.001, 100);

  Distrib(y, Normal, Prediction(y), SD_y);
  Distrib(z, Normal, Prediction(z), SD_z);

  A = 0;

  Experiment { # true y = 0 - 1 * x; true z = 0 + 1 * x
    PrintStep (y, 1, 10, 1);
    Data (y, -1.006879 -2.001636 -2.993538 -3.994545 -5.008485 -6.006281
          -6.977793 -8.004303 -8.999835 -9.992217);

    PrintStep (z, 1, 10, 1);
    Data (z, +1.006879 +2.001636 +2.993538 +3.994545 +5.008485 +6.006281
          +6.977793 +8.004303 +8.999835 +9.992217);
  }
}

End.
```

Supplementary Text S3. Stan script for the multi-modal linear regression test case.

```
/******  
LinearTwo.stan  
******/  
  
data {  
  int<lower=0>    nb      ;  
  real           x      [nb] ;  
  real           y1     [nb] ;  
  real           y2     [nb] ;  
}  
  
parameters {  
  real beta      ;  
  real log_sigma1 ;  
  real log_sigma2 ;  
}  
  
transformed parameters {  
  real sigma1 ;  
  real sigma2 ;  
  
  sigma1 = exp(log_sigma1) ;  
  sigma2 = exp(log_sigma2) ;  
}  
  
model {  
  beta ~ uniform(-10, 10) ;  
  log_sigma1 ~ uniform( log(0.001) , log(100));  
  log_sigma2 ~ uniform( log(0.001) , log(100));  
  
  for(i in 1:nb){  
    y1[i] ~ normal(beta * x[i], sigma1) ;  
    y2[i] ~ normal(beta * x[i], sigma2) ;  
  }  
}  
  
/* end */
```

Supplementary Text S4. GNU MCSim model for the Gaussian mean test case.

```
#-----  
# normal.model  
#  
# Inference about a mean, precision (inverse variance) known, from data  
# generated with that precision.  
#-----  
  
Outputs = {y};  
  
# Model Parameters  
mu      = 0;  
lambda = 0;  
  
CalcOutputs { y = mu + NormalRandom(0, lambda); }  
  
End.
```

Supplementary Text S5. MCSim MCMC script for the Gaussian mean test case.

```
#-----  
# normal.LTMCMC.in  
#  
# Normal model, thermodynamic integration MCMC sampling of mean mu.  
# True mean is 0, true precision is 1.  
#-----  
  
MCMC ("normal.LTMCMC.out",      # output file  
      "",                       # name of restart file  
      "",                       # name of data file  
      500000, 4,                # iterations, simtype flag  
      5, 500000,               # printing frequency, iters to print  
      4355631);               # random seed  
  
Level {  
  
  Distrib(mu, Normal, 0, 10); # exact mean  
  
  Likelihood(y, Normal, Prediction(y), 1); # exact SD  
  
  Simulation {  
    PrintStep (y, 1, 100, 1);  
  
    # note: y ~ N(0,1), sum(y) / 100 = -0.0631515  
    Data (y, -1.31559, -0.73666, 1.20569, -1.73722, -0.30884, -0.76155,  
            0.21518, 0.31707, -0.05521, 0.19057, 0.89541, 1.16196,  
            0.10125, 0.71446, 0.99934, 1.78996, -0.20972, 0.79051,  
            -0.82736, -0.57746, 0.28609, -0.89058, 0.33945, -2.03076,  
            0.62369, -0.35001, 1.75051, 0.64510, -0.86697, -1.58950,  
            2.08225, -1.60079, -0.33201, 0.61762, 1.00325, -0.76846,  
            -1.58168, -0.33435, -2.15645, 0.30864, 0.49061, 1.62940,  
            1.04681, 1.25895, 0.79866, 0.93647, -0.93496, -1.10015,  
            -0.63399, 0.16543, -0.87284, -0.25812, -0.14671, -1.16375,  
            -0.38878, 0.11945, 0.44588, 0.86473, 0.87712, -0.12696,  
            -0.10193, -0.32150, 0.07070, -0.32103, 0.37842, -1.82517,  
            0.86379, -0.52906, -0.86864, 0.48054, -1.71530, 2.25930,  
            -1.17660, -1.48330, 0.04143, 1.22078, -0.65970, -0.20954,  
            -1.66506, 0.31825, -1.86426, 1.31448, -0.92209, 0.39659,  
            0.20253, -0.36113, -0.68786, -0.61799, 1.11140, 0.62264,  
            0.58069, -0.74544, 0.81078, 1.32838, -0.38599, 0.52883,  
            -0.16352, -1.50377, 1.30310, -2.03298);  
  
  }  
}  
  
End.
```

Supplementary Text S6. GNU MCSim model for the theophylline population PK test case.

```
# =====
# Two-compartment model with first-order absorption rate and
# linear elimination (metabolism or other route of elimination)
#
# version 2
#
# Units:
# - time in hours
# - volumes in liters
# - masses of substances in micromoles
# - concentrations of substances in microM
# =====

States = {Q_central,      # Quantity in central compartment (micromoles)
          Q_periph,      # ~ peripheral compartment
          Q_to_release,  # ~ to release
          Q_gi,          # ~ in stomach (micromoles)
          Q_elim};      # ~ eliminated

Outputs = {C_central,    # Concentration in central compartment (microM)
           Q_total,      # Total quantity for mass balance
           lnQ_to_release,
           lnQ_gi,
           lnQ_periph,
           lnQ_elim,
           lnQ_total,
           lnC_central};

Inputs = {PO_dose,      # immediate dose, in micromoles / h
          IV_dose_rate};

# Default parameter values
# =====

# Dosage forms: 0/1 switches, mutually exclusive,
# only one on them should be set to 1
G_immediate = 1; # immediate release (default)
G_delayed = 0;

# Input setting
Period = 12.0; # period of the exposure/no exposure cycle (h)
TChng = 0.01; # infusion duration (h)
PO_dose = PerDose(1, Period, 0, 0.01);

# Rate constant (/h)
Kr; # Release rate
Ka; # Absorption rate
Ke; # Elimination rate

lnKr = log(1.0);
lnKa = log(1.0);
lnKe = log(0.05);

# Volumes (L)
# https://sepia.unil.ch/pharmacology/index.php?id=90
V_central;

lnV_central = log(0.3);

# Transfer rate constants between compartments (1/h)
Kc2p;
Kp2c;

lnKc2p = log(11);
lnKp2c = log(5);

# Statistical parameters
# =====
# Population mean
M_lnKr;
```

```

M_lnKa;
M_lnKe;
M_lnV_central;
M_lnKc2p;
M_lnKp2c;

# Variances inter individual
Vr_lnKr;
Vr_lnKa;
Vr_lnKe;
Vr_lnV_central;
Vr_lnKc2p;
Vr_lnKp2c;

# Variances intra individual
Va_lnKr;
Va_lnKa;
Va_lnKe;
Va_lnV_central;
Va_lnKc2p;
Va_lnKp2c;

# Data Error (Ve_...)
# =====
Ve_lnC_central;

Initialize {
    Kr      = exp(lnKr);
    Ka      = exp(lnKa);
    V_central = exp(lnV_central);
    Kc2p    = exp(lnKc2p);
    Kp2c    = exp(lnKp2c);
    Ke      = exp(lnKe);
} # End of model scaling

Dynamics {
    PO_dose_rate = PO_dose / TChng; # PO dose rate (into stomach) (mg/hr)

    dt (Q_to_release) = (G_immediate > 0.5 ? -1 :
        (G_delayed > 0.5 ? PO_dose_rate - Kr * Q_to_release :
        0.0));

    dt (Q_gi) = (G_immediate > 0.5 ? PO_dose_rate :
        (G_delayed > 0.5 ? Kr * Q_to_release : 0.0)) - Ka * Q_gi;

    dt (Q_elim) = Ke * Q_central;
    dt (Q_periph) = Kc2p * Q_central - Kp2c * Q_periph;
    dt (Q_central) = IV_dose_rate + Ka * Q_gi - dt(Q_elim) - dt(Q_periph);
}

CalcOutputs {
    C_central = (Q_central < 0 ? 0 : Q_central / V_central);

    Q_total = (G_immediate > 0.5 ? (Q_gi + Q_central + Q_periph + Q_elim) :
        (G_delayed > 0.5 ?
        Q_to_release + Q_gi + Q_central + Q_periph + Q_elim : 0.0));

    lnQ_to_release = (Q_to_release < 0 ? -50 : log(Q_to_release));
    lnQ_gi = (Q_gi < 0 ? -50 : log(Q_gi));
    lnQ_periph = (Q_periph < 0 ? -50 : log(Q_periph));
    lnQ_elim = (Q_elim < 0 ? -50 : log(Q_elim));
    lnQ_total = (Q_total < 0 ? -50 : log(Q_total));
    lnC_central = log(C_central);
}

End.

```

Supplementary Text S7. MCSim MCMC script 1 for the theophylline population PK test case.
Script for inter-individual variability population model.

```

#-----
# 2cpt.mcmc.inter.in
#-----

Integrate (Lsodes, 1e-7, 1e-9, 1);

MCMC ("theoph.LTMCMC.inter.out", "", "", 1, 20000, 4, 1, 20000, 1111);

Level { # population

  Distrib(M_lnKr,      Uniform,      -3.362245, -0.3665129);
  Distrib(M_lnKa,      Uniform,      -0.3665129, 1.9360720);
  Distrib(M_lnV_central, TruncNormal, 2.995732, 0.6931472, 1.609438, 4.382027);
  Distrib(M_lnKe,      TruncNormal, -1.347074, 0.6931472, -2.733368, 0.03922071);
  Distrib(M_lnKc2p,    TruncNormal, 0.0, 0.6931472, -1.386294, 1.386294);
  Distrib(M_lnKp2c,    TruncNormal, 0.9555114, 0.6931472, -0.4307829, 2.341806);

  # Inter individual variances:
  Distrib (Vr_lnKr,      InvGamma, 2.25, 0.3125);
  Distrib (Vr_lnKa,      InvGamma, 2.25, 0.3125);
  Distrib (Vr_lnV_central, InvGamma, 2.25, 0.3125);
  Distrib (Vr_lnKe,      InvGamma, 2.25, 0.3125);
  Distrib (Vr_lnKc2p,    InvGamma, 2.25, 0.3125);
  Distrib (Vr_lnKp2c,    InvGamma, 2.25, 0.3125);

  Distrib(Ve_lnC_central, LogUniform, 0.01, 0.5);
  Likelihood(lnC_central, Normal_v, Prediction(lnC_central), Ve_lnC_central);

Level { # individuals

  Distrib (lnKr,      TruncNormal_v, M_lnKr,      Vr_lnKr,      -3.362245, -0.3665129);
  Distrib (lnKa,      TruncNormal_v, M_lnKa,      Vr_lnKa,      -0.3665129, 1.9360720);
  Distrib (lnV_central, TruncNormal_v, M_lnV_central, Vr_lnV_central, 1.609438, 4.382027);
  Distrib (lnKe,      TruncNormal_v, M_lnKe,      Vr_lnKe,      -2.733368, 0.03922071);
  Distrib (lnKc2p,    TruncNormal_v, M_lnKc2p,    Vr_lnKc2p,    -1.386294, 1.386294);
  Distrib (lnKp2c,    TruncNormal_v, M_lnKp2c,    Vr_lnKp2c,    -0.4307829, 2.341806);

Level { # Subject 1,

  Period = 12.0; # period of the exposure/no exposure cycle (h)
  PO_dose = PerDose(1054.56, Period, 0, 0.01);

  Experiment { # Subject 1, Experiment 1

    G_immediate = 1; # immediate release, dissolved (default)
    G_delayed = 0; # delayed release, dissolved

    Print (lnC_central, 1 2 3 4 6 8 10 12);
    Data (lnC_central, 3.471712 3.418603 3.418603 3.261417 3.217932 -1 2.937630 -1);

  } # End Subject 1, Experiment 1

  Experiment { # Subject 1, Experiment 2

    G_immediate = 0; # immediate release, dissolved (default)
    G_delayed = 1; # delayed release, dissolved

    Print (lnC_central, 1 2 3 4 6 8 10 12);
    Data (lnC_central, 1.809165 2.301641 2.589323 2.407002 2.812467 3.261417 3.074831
          3.100149);

  } # End Subject 1, Experiment 2

  Experiment { # Subject 1, Experiment 3

    G_immediate = 0; # immediate release, dissolved (default)
    G_delayed = 1; # delayed release, dissolved

    Print (lnC_central, 73 74 75 76 78 80 82 84);
    Data (lnC_central, 3.645376 3.659765 3.853921 3.615962 3.471712 3.585657 3.522143
          3.522143);

  } # End Subject 1, Experiment 3

} # End Subject 1

Level { # subject 2,

  Period = 12.0; # period of the exposure/no exposure cycle (h)
  PO_dose = PerDose(1054.56, Period, 0, 0.01);

  Experiment { # Subject 1, Experiment 1

    G_immediate = 1; # immediate release, dissolved (default)
    G_delayed = 0; # delayed release, dissolved

    Print (lnC_central, 1 2 3 4 6 8 10 12);
    Data (lnC_central, 3.454321 3.585657 3.687935 3.454321 3.074831 3.074831 2.877005
          2.937630);

  }

  Experiment { # Subject 1, Experiment 2

    G_immediate = 0; # immediate release, dissolved (default)

```

```

G_delayed = 1; # delayed release, dissolved
Print (lnC_central, 1 2 3 4 6 8 10 12);
Data (lnC_central, 1.357179 2.355708 2.546764 2.845257 2.743474 2.502312 2.546764 2.669366);
}

Experiment { # Subject 2, Experiment 3
  G_immediate = 0; # immediate release, dissolved (default)
  G_delayed = 1; # delayed release, dissolved

  Print (lnC_central, 73 74 75 76 78 80 82 84);
  Data (lnC_central, 3.659765 3.687935 3.755075 3.755075 3.911079 3.830110 3.554404 3.659765);
} # End Subject 2, Experiment 3
} # end subject 2

Level { # subject 3,
  Period = 12.0; # period of the exposure/no exposure cycle (h)
  PO_dose = PerDose(1054.56, Period, 0, 0.01);

  Experiment { # Subject 1, Experiment 1
    G_immediate = 1; # immediate release, dissolved (default)
    G_delayed = 0; # delayed release, dissolved

    Print (lnC_central, 1 2 3 4 6 8 10 12);
    Data (lnC_central, 3.911079 3.381561 3.381561 3.381561 3.172469 2.966617 2.877005 2.669366);
  }

  Experiment { # Subject 1, Experiment 2
    G_immediate = 0; # immediate release, dissolved (default)
    G_delayed = 1; # delayed release, dissolved

    Print (lnC_central, 1 2 3 4 6 8 10 12);
    Data (lnC_central, -1 2.502312 2.778565 3.022187 3.100149 2.937630 -1 -1);
  }

  Experiment { # Subject 3, Experiment 3
    Period = 12.0; # period of the exposure/no exposure cycle (h)
    PO_dose = PerDose(1054.56, Period, 0, 0.01);

    G_immediate = 0; # immediate release, dissolved (default)
    G_delayed = 1; # delayed release, dissolved

    Print (lnC_central, 73 74 75 76 78 80 82 84);
    Data (lnC_central, 3.780717 3.985980 4.129768 4.181954 4.181954 3.817989 3.755075 3.645376);
  } # End Subject 3, Experiment 3
} # End subject 3

Level { # subject 4,
  Experiment { # Subject 4, Experiment 1
    Period = 12.0; # period of the exposure/no exposure cycle (h)
    PO_dose = PerDose(1054.56, Period, 0, 0.01);
    G_immediate = 1; # immediate release, dissolved (default)
    G_delayed = 0; # delayed release, dissolved

    Print (lnC_central, 1 2 3 4 6 8 10 12);
    Data (lnC_central, 3.362513 3.343095 3.217932 3.124841 3.124841 3.124841 2.877005 2.669366);
  }

  Experiment { # Subject 4, Experiment 2
    Period = 12.0; # period of the exposure/no exposure cycle (h)
    PO_dose = PerDose(1054.56, Period, 0, 0.01);
    G_immediate = 0; # immediate release, dissolved (default)
    G_delayed = 1; # delayed release, dissolved

    Print (lnC_central, 1 2 3 4 6 8 10 12);
    Data (lnC_central, 1.809165 2.244483 2.407002 2.407002 2.589323 2.743474 2.669366 2.907777);
  }

  Experiment { # Subject 4, Experiment 3
    Period = 12.0; # period of the exposure/no exposure cycle (h)
    PO_dose = PerDose(1054.56, Period, 0, 0.01);
    G_immediate = 0; # immediate release, dissolved (default)
    G_delayed = 1; # delayed release, dissolved

    Print (lnC_central, 73 74 75 76 78 80 82 84);
    Data (lnC_central, 3.418603 3.538404 3.381561 3.538404 3.659765 3.048855 2.812467 2.994788);
  } # End Subject 4, Experiment 3

  Experiment { # Subject 4, Experiment 4
    Period = 12.0; # period of the exposure/no exposure cycle (h)
    PO_dose = PerDose(2109.12, Period, 0, 0.01);
    G_immediate = 0; # immediate release, dissolved (default)
    G_delayed = 1; # delayed release, dissolved

```

```

    Print (lnC_central, 73 74 75 76 78 80 82 84);
    Data (lnC_central, 4.709587 4.729389 4.673960 4.709587 4.626205 4.467515 4.345743 4.223454);
} # Subject 4, Experiment 4
} # end subject 4
Level { # subject 5,
  Period = 12.0; # period of the exposure/no exposure cycle (h)
  PO_dose = PerDose(1054.56, Period, 0, 0.01);
  Experiment { # Subject 5, Experiment 1
    G_immediate = 1; # immediate release, dissolved (default)
    G_delayed = 0; # delayed release, dissolved
    Print (lnC_central, 1 2 3 4 6 8 10 12);
    Data (lnC_central, 3.148939 3.124841 2.966617 2.778565 2.630145 2.050327 1.896176 1.809165);
  }
  Experiment { # Subject 5, Experiment 2
    G_immediate = 0; # immediate release, dissolved (default)
    G_delayed = 1; # delayed release, dissolved
    Print (lnC_central, 1 2 3 4 6 8 10 12);
    Data (lnC_central, -1 -1 1.713854 2.407002 2.589323 2.589323 2.183858 2.301641);
  }
  Experiment { # Subject 5, Experiment 3
    G_immediate = 0; # immediate release, dissolved (default)
    G_delayed = 1; # delayed release, dissolved
    Print (lnC_central, 73 74 75 76 78 80 82 84);
    Data (lnC_central, 2.743474 2.812467 2.778565 2.630145 2.455792 2.244483 2.244483 2.244483);
  } # End Subject 5, Experiment 3
} # end subject 5
Level { # subject 6,
  Experiment { # Subject 6, Experiment 1
    Period = 12.0; # period of the exposure/no exposure cycle (h)
    PO_dose = PerDose(1054.56, Period, 0, 0.01);
    G_immediate = 1; # immediate release, dissolved (default)
    G_delayed = 0; # delayed release, dissolved
    Print (lnC_central, 1 2 3 4 6 8 10 12);
    Data (lnC_central, 2.877005 2.907777 2.877005 2.743474 2.301641 2.050327 1.809165 1.809165);
  }
  Experiment { # Subject 6, Experiment 2
    Period = 12.0; # period of the exposure/no exposure cycle (h)
    PO_dose = PerDose(1054.56, Period, 0, 0.01);
    G_immediate = 0; # immediate release, dissolved (default)
    G_delayed = 1; # delayed release, dissolved
    Print (lnC_central, 1 2 3 4 6 8 10 12);
    Data (lnC_central, -1 -1 2.183858 2.244483 2.301641 2.907777 2.630145 2.778565);
  }
  Experiment { # Subject 6, Experiment 3
    Period = 12.0; # period of the exposure/no exposure cycle (h)
    PO_dose = PerDose(1054.56, Period, 0, 0.01);
    G_immediate = 0; # immediate release, dissolved (default)
    G_delayed = 1; # delayed release, dissolved
    Print (lnC_central, 73 74 75 76 78 80 82 84);
    Data (lnC_central, 3.022187 2.877005 3.148939 3.100149 3.074831 2.707106 2.669366 2.455792);
  } # End Subject 6, Experiment 3
  Experiment { # Subject 6, Experiment 4
    Period = 12.0; # period of the exposure/no exposure cycle (h)
    PO_dose = PerDose(2109.12, Period, 0, 0.01);
    G_immediate = 0; # immediate release, dissolved (default)
    G_delayed = 1; # delayed release, dissolved
    Print (lnC_central, 73 74 75 76 78 80 82 84);
    Data (lnC_central, 3.659765 3.865617 3.865617 3.817989 3.630777 3.323292 3.522143 3.239911);
  } # Subject 6, Experiment 4
} # end subject 6
} # end subjects
} # end pop
End.

```

Supplementary Text S8. MCSim MCMC script 2 for the theophylline population PK test case.
Script for inter- and intra-individual variability population model.

```

#-----
# 2cpt.mcmc.intra.in
#-----

Integrate (Lsodes, 1e-7, 1e-9, 1);

MCMC ("theoph.LTMCMC.intra.out", "", "", 1, 20000, 4, 1, 20000, 1111);

Level { # population

Distrib(M_lnKr,          Uniform,      -3.0, -1.0);
Distrib(M_lnKa,          Uniform,         1.0,  2.3);
Distrib(M_lnV_central,  TruncNormal,  3.56, 1,      2.06,  5.06);
Distrib(M_lnKe,          TruncNormal, -1.68, 0.5, -2.68, -0.68);
Distrib(M_lnKc2p,        TruncNormal,  2.41, 0.5,  1.41,  3.41);
Distrib(M_lnKp2c,        TruncNormal,  1.61, 0.5,  0.61,  2.61);

# Inter individual variances:
Distrib (Vr_lnKr,          InvGamma,    2.25, 0.3125);
Distrib (Vr_lnKa,          InvGamma,    2.25, 0.3125);
Distrib (Vr_lnV_central,  InvGamma,    2.25, 0.3125);
Distrib (Vr_lnKe,          InvGamma,    2.25, 0.3125);
Distrib (Vr_lnKc2p,        InvGamma,    2.25, 0.3125);
Distrib (Vr_lnKp2c,        InvGamma,    2.25, 0.3125);

# Intra individual variances:
Distrib (Va_lnKr,          InvGamma,    2.25, 0.3125);
Distrib (Va_lnKa,          InvGamma,    2.25, 0.3125);
Distrib (Va_lnV_central,  InvGamma,    2.25, 0.3125);
Distrib (Va_lnKe,          InvGamma,    2.25, 0.3125);
Distrib (Va_lnKc2p,        InvGamma,    2.25, 0.3125);
Distrib (Va_lnKp2c,        InvGamma,    2.25, 0.3125);

Distrib(Ve_lnC_central, LogUniform, 0.01, 0.5);
Likelihood(lnC_central, Normal_v, Prediction(lnC_central), Ve_lnC_central);

Level { # individuals

Distrib (lnKr,          TruncNormal_v, M_lnKr,          Vr_lnKr,          -3.0, -1.0);
Distrib (lnKa,          TruncNormal_v, M_lnKa,          Vr_lnKa,           1.0,  2.3);
Distrib (lnV_central,  TruncNormal_v, M_lnV_central, Vr_lnV_central,  2.06,  5.06);
Distrib (lnKe,          TruncNormal_v, M_lnKe,          Vr_lnKe,          -2.68, -0.68);
Distrib (lnKc2p,        TruncNormal_v, M_lnKc2p,        Vr_lnKc2p,         1.41,  3.41);
Distrib (lnKp2c,        TruncNormal_v, M_lnKp2c,        Vr_lnKp2c,         0.61,  2.61);

Level { # subject M,

Distrib (lnKr,          TruncNormal_v, M_lnKr,          Va_lnKr,          -3.0, -1.0);
Distrib (lnKa,          TruncNormal_v, M_lnKa,          Va_lnKa,           1.0,  2.3);
Distrib (lnV_central,  TruncNormal_v, M_lnV_central, Va_lnV_central,  2.06,  5.06);
Distrib (lnKe,          TruncNormal_v, M_lnKe,          Va_lnKe,          -2.68, -0.68);
Distrib (lnKc2p,        TruncNormal_v, M_lnKc2p,        Va_lnKc2p,         1.41,  3.41);
Distrib (lnKp2c,        TruncNormal_v, M_lnKp2c,        Va_lnKp2c,         0.61,  2.61);

Period = 12.0; # period of the exposure/no exposure cycle (h)
PO_dose = PerDose(1054.56, Period, 0, 0.01);

Experiment { # Subject M, Experiment 1 IR

Print (lnC_central, 1 2 3 4 6 8 10 12);
Data (lnC_central, 3.471712 3.418603 3.418603 3.261417 3.217932 -1 2.937630 -1);

} # End Subject M, Experiment 1

Experiment { # Subject M, Experiment 2 SR

G_immediate = 0;
G_delayed = 1;

Print (lnC_central, 1 2 3 4 6 8 10 12);
Data (lnC_central, 1.809165 2.301641 2.589323 2.407002 2.812467 3.261417 3.074831 3.100149);

} # End Subject M, Experiment 2

Experiment { # Subject M, Experiment 3 SR

G_immediate = 0;
G_delayed = 1;

Print (lnC_central, 73 74 75 76 78 80 82 84);
Data (lnC_central, 3.645376 3.659765 3.853921 3.615962 3.471712 3.585657 3.522143 3.522143);

} # End Subject M, Experiment 3

} # end subject M

Level { # subject N,

Distrib (lnKr,          TruncNormal_v, M_lnKr,          Va_lnKr,          -3.0, -1.0);
Distrib (lnKa,          TruncNormal_v, M_lnKa,          Va_lnKa,           1.0,  2.3);
Distrib (lnV_central,  TruncNormal_v, M_lnV_central, Va_lnV_central,  2.06,  5.06);
Distrib (lnKe,          TruncNormal_v, M_lnKe,          Va_lnKe,          -2.68, -0.68);
Distrib (lnKc2p,        TruncNormal_v, M_lnKc2p,        Va_lnKc2p,         1.41,  3.41);
Distrib (lnKp2c,        TruncNormal_v, M_lnKp2c,        Va_lnKp2c,         0.61,  2.61);

```

```

Period = 12.0; # period of the exposure/no exposure cycle (h)
PO_dose = PerDose(1054.56, Period, 0, 0.01);

Experiment { # Subject 1, Experiment 1 IR
  Print (lnC_central, 1 2 3 4 6 8 10 12);
  Data (lnC_central, 3.454321 3.585657 3.687935 3.454321 3.074831 3.074831 2.877005 2.937630);
}

Experiment { # Subject 1, Experiment 2 SR
  G_immediate = 0;
  G_delayed = 1;

  Print (lnC_central, 1 2 3 4 6 8 10 12);
  Data (lnC_central, 1.357179 2.355708 2.546764 2.845257 2.743474 2.502312 2.546764 2.669366);
}

Experiment { # Subject N, Experiment 3 SR
  G_immediate = 0;
  G_delayed = 1;

  Print (lnC_central, 73 74 75 76 78 80 82 84);
  Data (lnC_central, 3.659765 3.687935 3.755075 3.755075 3.911079 3.830110 3.554404 3.659765);
} # End Subject N, Experiment 3
} # end subject N

Level { # subject O,
  Distrib (lnKr,          TruncNormal_v, M_lnKr,          Va_lnKr,          -3.0,  -1.0);
  Distrib (lnKa,          TruncNormal_v, M_lnKa,          Va_lnKa,          1.0,   2.3);
  Distrib (lnV_central,   TruncNormal_v, M_lnV_central, Va_lnV_central,   2.06,  5.06);
  Distrib (lnKe,          TruncNormal_v, M_lnKe,          Va_lnKe,          -2.68, -0.68);
  Distrib (lnKc2p,       TruncNormal_v, M_lnKc2p,       Va_lnKc2p,        1.41,  3.41);
  Distrib (lnKp2c,       TruncNormal_v, M_lnKp2c,       Va_lnKp2c,        0.61,  2.61);

  Period = 12.0; # period of the exposure/no exposure cycle (h)
  PO_dose = PerDose(1054.56, Period, 0, 0.01);

  Experiment { # Subject 1, Experiment 1
    Print (lnC_central, 1 2 3 4 6 8 10 12);
    Data (lnC_central, 3.911079 3.381561 3.381561 3.381561 3.172469 2.966617 2.877005 2.669366);
  }

  Experiment { # Subject 1, Experiment 2
    G_immediate = 0;
    G_delayed = 1;

    Print (lnC_central, 1 2 3 4 6 8 10 12);
    Data (lnC_central, -1 2.502312 2.778565 3.022187 3.100149 2.937630          -1          -1);
  }

  Experiment { # Subject O, Experiment 3
    Period = 12.0; # period of the exposure/no exposure cycle (h)
    PO_dose = PerDose(1054.56, Period, 0, 0.01);

    G_immediate = 0;
    G_delayed = 1;

    Print (lnC_central, 73 74 75 76 78 80 82 84);
    Data (lnC_central, 3.780717 3.985980 4.129768 4.181954 4.181954 3.817989 3.755075 3.645376);
  } # End Subject O, Experiment 3
} # end subject O

Level { # subject P,
  Distrib (lnKr,          TruncNormal_v, M_lnKr,          Va_lnKr,          -3.0,  -1.0);
  Distrib (lnKa,          TruncNormal_v, M_lnKa,          Va_lnKa,          1.0,   2.3);
  Distrib (lnV_central,   TruncNormal_v, M_lnV_central, Va_lnV_central,   2.06,  5.06);
  Distrib (lnKe,          TruncNormal_v, M_lnKe,          Va_lnKe,          -2.68, -0.68);
  Distrib (lnKc2p,       TruncNormal_v, M_lnKc2p,       Va_lnKc2p,        1.41,  3.41);
  Distrib (lnKp2c,       TruncNormal_v, M_lnKp2c,       Va_lnKp2c,        0.61,  2.61);

  Period = 12.0; # period of the exposure/no exposure cycle (h)

  Experiment { # Subject P, Experiment 1 IR
    PO_dose = PerDose(1054.56, Period, 0, 0.01);

    Print (lnC_central, 1 2 3 4 6 8 10 12);
    Data (lnC_central, 3.362513 3.343095 3.217932 3.124841 3.124841 3.124841 2.877005 2.669366);
  }

  Experiment { # Subject P, Experiment 2 SR
    PO_dose = PerDose(1054.56, Period, 0, 0.01);

    G_immediate = 0;
    G_delayed = 1;

```

```

Print (lnC_central, 1 2 3 4 6 8 10 12);
Data (lnC_central, 1.809165 2.244483 2.407002 2.407002 2.589323 2.743474 2.669366 2.907777);
}

Experiment { # Subject P, Experiment 3 SR
  PO_dose = PerDose(1054.56, Period, 0, 0.01);

  G_immediate = 0;
  G_delayed = 1;

  Print (lnC_central, 73 74 75 76 78 80 82 84);
  Data (lnC_central, 3.418603 3.538404 3.381561 3.538404 3.659765 3.048855 2.812467 2.994788);
} # End Subject P, Experiment 3

Experiment { # Subject P, Experiment 4 SR-high dose
  PO_dose = PerDose(2109.12, Period, 0, 0.01);

  G_immediate = 0;
  G_delayed = 1;

  Print (lnC_central, 73 74 75 76 78 80 82 84);
  Data (lnC_central, 4.709587 4.729389 4.673960 4.709587 4.626205 4.467515 4.345743 4.223454);
} # Subject P, Experiment 4
} # end subject P

Level { # subject Q,
  Distrib (lnKr,          TruncNormal_v, M_lnKr,          Va_lnKr,          -3.0, -1.0);
  Distrib (lnKa,          TruncNormal_v, M_lnKa,          Va_lnKa,          1.0, 2.3);
  Distrib (lnV_central,   TruncNormal_v, M_lnV_central, Va_lnV_central,   2.06, 5.06);
  Distrib (lnKe,          TruncNormal_v, M_lnKe,          Va_lnKe,          -2.68, -0.68);
  Distrib (lnKc2p,        TruncNormal_v, M_lnKc2p,        Va_lnKc2p,        1.41, 3.41);
  Distrib (lnKp2c,        TruncNormal_v, M_lnKp2c,        Va_lnKp2c,        0.61, 2.61);

  Period = 12.0; # period of the exposure/no exposure cycle (h)
  PO_dose = PerDose(1054.56, Period, 0, 0.01);

  Experiment { # Subject Q, Experiment 1 IR
    Print (lnC_central, 1 2 3 4 6 8 10 12);
    Data (lnC_central, 3.148939 3.124841 2.966617 2.778565 2.630145 2.050327 1.896176 1.809165);
  }

  Experiment { # Subject Q, Experiment 2 SR
    G_immediate = 0; # immediate release, dissolved (default)
    G_delayed = 1; # delayed release, dissolved

    Print (lnC_central, 1 2 3 4 6 8 10 12);
    Data (lnC_central, -1 -1 1.713854 2.407002 2.589323 2.589323 2.183858 2.301641);
  }

  Experiment { # Subject Q, Experiment 3 SR
    G_immediate = 0; # immediate release, dissolved (default)
    G_delayed = 1; # delayed release, dissolved

    Print (lnC_central, 73 74 75 76 78 80 82 84);
    Data (lnC_central, 2.743474 2.812467 2.778565 2.630145 2.455792 2.244483 2.244483 2.244483);
  } # End Subject Q, Experiment 3
} # end subject Q

Level { # subject R,
  Distrib (lnKr,          TruncNormal_v, M_lnKr,          Va_lnKr,          -3.0, -1.0);
  Distrib (lnKa,          TruncNormal_v, M_lnKa,          Va_lnKa,          1.0, 2.3);
  Distrib (lnV_central,   TruncNormal_v, M_lnV_central, Va_lnV_central,   2.06, 5.06);
  Distrib (lnKe,          TruncNormal_v, M_lnKe,          Va_lnKe,          -2.68, -0.68);
  Distrib (lnKc2p,        TruncNormal_v, M_lnKc2p,        Va_lnKc2p,        1.41, 3.41);
  Distrib (lnKp2c,        TruncNormal_v, M_lnKp2c,        Va_lnKp2c,        0.61, 2.61);

  Period = 12.0; # period of the exposure/no exposure cycle (h)

  Experiment { # Subject R, Experiment 1 IR
    PO_dose = PerDose(1054.56, Period, 0, 0.01);

    Print (lnC_central, 1 2 3 4 6 8 10 12);
    Data (lnC_central, 2.877005 2.907777 2.877005 2.743474 2.301641 2.050327 1.809165 1.809165);
  }

  Experiment { # Subject R, Experiment 2 SR
    PO_dose = PerDose(1054.56, Period, 0, 0.01);
    G_immediate = 0;
    G_delayed = 1;

    Print (lnC_central, 1 2 3 4 6 8 10 12);
    Data (lnC_central, -1 -1 2.183858 2.244483 2.301641 2.907777 2.630145 2.778565);
  }

  Experiment { # Subject R, Experiment 3 SR

```

```

PO_dose = PerDose(1054.56, Period, 0, 0.01);
G_immediate = 0;
G_delayed = 1;

Print (lnC_central, 73 74 75 76 78 80 82 84);
Data (lnC_central, 3.022187 2.877005 3.148939 3.100149 3.074831 2.707106 2.669366 2.455792);

} # End Subject R, Experiment 3

Experiment { # Subject R, Experiment 4 SR-high dose

PO_dose = PerDose(2109.12, Period, 0, 0.01);
G_immediate = 0;
G_delayed = 1;

Print (lnC_central, 73 74 75 76 78 80 82 84);
Data (lnC_central, 3.659765 3.865617 3.865617 3.817989 3.630777 3.323292 3.522143 3.239911);

} # Subject R, Experiment 4

} # end subject R
} # end subjects
} # end pop

End.

```

Supplementary Text S9. GNU MCSim model for the acetaminophen PBPK test case.

```
#-----
#                               Initial Parameters
#                               (plus params for added compartments)
#-----
#region

# Chemical Parameters
#-----
MW_APAP = 151.17;           # Molecular Weight of APAP
MW_AG = 327.28;           # Molecular Weight of APAP-glucoronide
MW_AS = 231.22;           # Molecular Weight of APAP-suphate
#fa = 0.87; lnfa = log(0.87); # Bioavailability of APAP

# Anatomical Parameters
#-----
BW = 70.; lnBW = log(70.); # Body weight (kg).
QCC = 16.2; lnQCC = log(16.2); # Cardiac output (L/hr/kg^0.75).

# Fractional volumes (fraction of body weight).
VFC = 0.214; lnVFC = log(0.214); # Fat.
VKC = 0.0044; lnVKC = log(0.0044); # Kidney.
VGC = 0.0144; lnVGC = log(0.0144); # Gut.
VLC = 0.0257; lnVLC = log(0.0257); # Liver.
VMC = 0.4; lnVMC = log(0.4); # Muscle
VBLAC= 0.0243; lnVBLAC = log(0.0243); # Arterial Blood.
VBLVC= 0.0557; lnVBLVC = log(0.0557); # Venous Blood.
VSC = 0.185; lnVSC = log(0.185); # Slowly Perfused
VRC = 0.0765; lnVRC = log(0.0765); # Rapidly Perfused (1- everything else)

# Fractional blood flows (fraction of cardiac output).
QFC = 0.052; lnQFC = log(0.052); # Fat. **
QKC = 0.175; lnQKC = log(0.175); # Kidney.
QGC = 0.181; lnQGC = log(0.181); # Gut. **
QLBC = 0.046; lnQLBC = log(0.046); # Hepatic artery. **
QMC = 0.191; lnQMC = log(0.191); # Muscle
QSC = 0.14; lnQSC = log(0.14); # Slowly Perfused
QRC = 0.215; lnQRC = log(0.215); # Rapidly Perfused (1 - everything else)

# Chemical Specific Transport Params
#-----
kSG_Vm = 2332.5; lnkSG_Vm = log(2332.5); # Kmax for abs to portal
kSG_Km = 1765.49; lnkSG_Km = log(1765.49); # Km for abs to portal
Tg = 0.233; lnTg = log(0.233);
Tp = 0.033; lnTp = log(0.033);

CLC_APAP = 0.059; lnCLC_APAP = log(0.059); # Total APAP blood clearance (L/hr/kg)
CLC_AS = 0.29; lnCLC_AS = log(0.29); # Total AS blood clearance (L/hr/kg)
CLC_AG = 0.22; lnCLC_AG = log(0.22); # Total AG blood clearance (L/hr/kg)
alpha_APAP = 1.;
alpha_AS = 1.;
alpha_AG = 1.;

BP_APAP = 0.9; lnBP_APAP = log(0.9); # Blood:Plasma Ratio

# Partition Coefficients
# Rodgers et al. APAP: pKa1 = 9.46, pKa2 = -4.4, zwitterion, logP = 0.91, fu = 0.819, BP = 0.98
PF_APAP = 0.447; lnPF_APAP = log(0.447); # Fat:blood
PG_APAP = 0.907; lnPG_APAP = log(0.907); # Gut:blood
PK_APAP = 0.711; lnPK_APAP = log(0.711); # Kidney:blood
PL_APAP = 0.687; lnPL_APAP = log(0.687); # Liver:blood
PM_APAP = 0.687; lnPM_APAP = log(0.687); # Muscle:blood

PR_APAP = 0.676; lnPR_APAP = log(0.676); # rapidly perfused:blood [brain, lung, spleen]
PS_APAP = 0.606; lnPS_APAP = log(0.606); # slowly perfused:blood [bone, heart, skin]

# Rodgers et al. AS: pKa1 = -2.2, pKa2 = -4.4, zwitterion, logP = -1, fu = 0.46, BP = 0.98
PF_AS = 0.088; lnPF_AS = log(0.088);
PG_AS = 0.297; lnPG_AS = log(0.297);
PK_AS = 0.261; lnPK_AS = log(0.261);
PL_AS = 0.203; lnPL_AS = log(0.203);
PM_AS = 0.199; lnPM_AS = log(0.199);

PR_AS = 0.207; lnPR_AS = log(0.207);
PS_AS = 0.254; lnPS_AS = log(0.254);

# Rodgers et al. AG: pKa1 = 3.17, pKa2 = -3.7, zwitterion, logP = -0.68, fu = 0.923, BP = 0.98
PF_AG = 0.128; lnPF_AG = log(0.128);
PG_AG = 0.436; lnPG_AG = log(0.436);
PK_AG = 0.392; lnPK_AG = log(0.392);
PL_AG = 0.321; lnPL_AG = log(0.321);
PM_AG = 0.336; lnPM_AG = log(0.336);

PR_AG = 0.364; lnPR_AG = log(0.364);
PS_AG = 0.351; lnPS_AG = log(0.351);
```

```

# Biochemical Parameters
#-----

# PAPS second order rate constant
#-----
kPAPS = 0.018; lnkPAPS = log(0.018);
kPAPS_syn = 1E-20; lnkPAPS_syn = log(1E-20); # Zeroth order PAPS synthesis

# GA second order rate constant
#-----
kGA = 0.008; lnkGA = log(0.008);
kGA_syn = 1E-20; lnkGA_syn = log(1E-20); # Zeroth order GA synthesis

#CYP Oxidase Params (Liver)
#-----
CYP_Km = 2082.; lnCYP_Km = log(2082.);
CYP_VmaxC = 4623.; lnCYP_VmaxC = log(4623.);

# Glucoronidation (Liver)
#-----
UGT_Km = 6000.; lnUGT_Km = log(6000.); # Km for entire UGT 2
UGT_Ki = 1E10; lnUGT_Ki = log(1E10); # Partial substrate inhibition for UGT
UGT_VmaxC = 1551.; lnUGT_VmaxC = log(1551.); # Vmax in Liver
UGT_Km_GA = 10.; lnUGT_Km_GA = log(10.); # Km for UGT cofactor
Vmax_AG = 1E20; lnVmax_AG = log(1E20); # Vmax for transport out of hepatocyte
Km_AG = 20000.; lnKm_AG = log(20000.); # Km for transport out of hepatocyte

# Sulfation by PAPS (Liver)
#-----
SULT_Km_apap = 300.; lnSULT_Km_apap = log(300.);
SULT_Km_paps = 19.65; lnSULT_Km_paps = log(19.65);
SULT_Ki = 1E10; lnSULT_Ki = log(1E10); # Partial substrate inhibition for SULT
SULT_VmaxC = 43100.; lnSULT_VmaxC = log(43100.); # Vmax in Liver
Vmax_AS = 1.0E20; lnVmax_AS = log(1.0E20); # Vmax for AS transport out of hepatocyte
Km_AS = 22900.; lnKm_AS = log(22900.); # Km for AS transport out of hepatocyte

#endregion

#-----
# Parameters for Exposure/Dose
#-----
#region
mgkg_flag=1.; # If the flag is 1, we have a mg/kg dose

# Oral Regimen
OralDose_APAP_mgkg = 0.; lnOralDose_APAP_mgkg = log(2E-9); # Oral Dose given (mg/kg)
OralDose_APAP_mg = 0.; lnOralDose_APAP_mg = log(2E-9); # Oral Dose given (mg)

OralDur_APAP = 0.001; # Oral Duration of chemical (hr)
ODose_APAP_mg; # Calculated Dose of APAP (mg)
fa; # Calculated, dose dependent fa
ODose_APAP; # Dose of chemical (muM/hr)
true_dose; # Calculated dose (muM)

# IV Regimen
IVDose_APAP_mgkg = 0.; lnIVDose_APAP_mgkg = log(2E-9); # IV Dose given (mg/kg)
IVDose_APAP_mg = 0.; lnIVDose_APAP_mg = log(2E-9); # IV Dose given (mg)

IVDur_APAP = 0.001; # IV Duration (hr): Default is 5 min duration
IVDose_APAP_mg; # Calculated Dose of APAP (mg)
IVDR_APAP; # Actual Dose of APAP (muM)
#endregion

#-----
# Defined Scaled Parameters
#-----
#region
# Metabolism Vmax
CYP_Vmax; UGT_Vmax; SULT_Vmax;

# Compartment Volumes
VTC; VF; VK; VG; VM; VL; VBLA; VBLV; VR; VS;

# Compartment Flow Rates
QTC; QC; QF; QK; QG; QM; QLB; QR; QS; QL;

# Clearance Rates
CLR_APAP; CLR_AS; CLR_AG;
#endregion

#-----
# Reverse Dosimetry Parameters
#-----
#region
M_OralDose_APAP; Var_OralDose_APAP;
M_IVDose_APAP; Var_IVDose_APAP;
M_lnOralDose_APAP; Var_lnOralDose_APAP;
M_lnIVDose_APAP; M_lnVar_IVDose_APAP;
#endregion

```

```

#-----
#                               Calibration Parameters
#-----
#region

#-----
#                               Population Mean Parameters (M_...)
#-----
#region
# Physiological Params
#-----
M_BW; M_lnBW;
M_fa; M_lnfa;

#
M_lnQCC;
#
M_lnVFC;
M_lnVKC;
M_lnVGC;
M_lnVLC;
M_lnVMC;
M_lnVBLAC;
M_lnVBLVC;
M_lnVSC;
M_lnVRC;
M_lnQFC;
M_lnQKC;
M_lnQGC;
M_lnQLBC;
M_lnQMC;
M_lnQSC;
M_lnQRC;

# Chemical Specific Transport Params
#-----
M_kSG_Vm; M_lnkSG_Vm;
M_kSG_Km; M_lnkSG_Km;
M_Tg;      M_lnTg;
M_Tp;      M_lnTp;

#
M_CLC_APAP; M_lnCLC_APAP; # Total APAP blood clearance (L/hr/kg)
M_CLC_AS; M_lnCLC_AS; # Total AS blood clearance (L/hr/kg)
M_CLC_AG; M_lnCLC_AG; # Total AG blood clearance (L/hr/kg)

M_BP_APAP; M_lnBP_APAP; # Blood:Plasma Ratio
# Rodgers et al.
# APAP
M_PF_APAP; M_lnPF_APAP; # Fat:blood
M_PG_APAP; M_lnPG_APAP; # Gut:blood
M_PK_APAP; M_lnPK_APAP; # Kidney:blood
M_PL_APAP; M_lnPL_APAP; # Liver:blood
M_PM_APAP; M_lnPM_APAP; # Muscle:blood
M_PR_APAP; M_lnPR_APAP; # rapidly perfused:blood
M_PS_APAP; M_lnPS_APAP; # slowly perfused:blood

# AS
M_PK_AS; M_lnPK_AS;
M_PF_AS; M_lnPF_AS;
M_PL_AS; M_lnPL_AS;
M_PG_AS; M_lnPG_AS;
M_PM_AS; M_lnPM_AS;
M_PR_AS; M_lnPR_AS;
M_PS_AS; M_lnPS_AS;

# AG
M_PK_AG; M_lnPK_AG;
M_PF_AG; M_lnPF_AG;
M_PL_AG; M_lnPL_AG;
M_PG_AG; M_lnPG_AG;
M_PM_AG; M_lnPM_AG;
M_PR_AG; M_lnPR_AG;
M_PS_AG; M_lnPS_AG;

# Biochemical Parameters
#-----
# PAPS second order rate constant
#-----
M_kPAPS; M_lnkPAPS;
M_kPAPS_syn; M_lnkPAPS_syn;

# GA second order rate constant
#-----
M_kGA; M_lnkGA;
M_kGA_syn; M_lnkGA_syn;

#CYP Oxidase Params (Liver)

```

```

#-----
M_CYP_Km; M_lnCYP_Km;
M_CYP_VmaxC; M_lnCYP_VmaxC;

# Glucoronidation (Liver)
#-----
M_UGT_Km; M_lnUGT_Km;          # Km for entire UGT 2
M_UGT_VmaxC; M_lnUGT_VmaxC;   # Vmax in Liver
M_UGT_Km_GA; M_lnUGT_Km_GA;
M_UGT_Ki; M_lnUGT_Ki;
M_Vmax_AG; M_lnVmax_AG;
M_Km_AG; M_lnKm_AG;

# Sulfation by PAPS (Liver)
#-----
M_SULT_Km_apap; M_lnSULT_Km_apap;
M_SULT_Km_paps; M_lnSULT_Km_paps;
M_SULT_Ki; M_lnSULT_Ki;
M_SULT_VmaxC; M_lnSULT_VmaxC; # Vmax in Liver
M_Vmax_AS; M_lnVmax_AS;
M_Km_AS; M_lnKm_AS;
#endregion

#-----
# Population Variance Parameters (Var_...)
#-----
#region
# Physiological Params
#-----
Var_BW; Var_lnBW;
Var_fa; Var_lnfa;

Var_lnQCC;

Var_lnVFC;
Var_lnVKC;
Var_lnVGC;
Var_lnVLC;
Var_lnVMC;
Var_lnVBLAC;
Var_lnVBLVC;
Var_lnVSC;
Var_lnVRC;
Var_lnQFC;
Var_lnQKC;
Var_lnQGC;
Var_lnQLBC;
Var_lnQMC;
Var_lnQSC;
Var_lnQRC;

# Chemical Specific Transport Params
#-----
Var_kSG_Vm; Var_lnkSG_Vm;
Var_kSG_Km; Var_lnkSG_Km;
Var_Tg; Var_lnTg;
Var_Tp; Var_lnTp;

Var_CLC_APAP; Var_lnCLC_APAP; # Total APAP blood clearance (L/hr/kg)
Var_CLC_AS; Var_lnCLC_AS; # Total AS blood clearance (L/hr/kg)
Var_CLC_AG; Var_lnCLC_AG; # Total AG blood clearance (L/hr/kg)

Var_BP_APAP; Var_lnBP_APAP; # Blood:Plasma Ratio
# Rodgers et al.
# APAP
Var_PF_APAP; Var_lnPF_APAP; # Fat:blood
Var_PG_APAP; Var_lnPG_APAP; # Gut:blood
Var_PK_APAP; Var_lnPK_APAP; # Kidney:blood
Var_PL_APAP; Var_lnPL_APAP; # Liver:blood
Var_PM_APAP; Var_lnPM_APAP; # Muscle:blood
Var_PR_APAP; Var_lnPR_APAP; # rapidly perfused:blood
Var_PS_APAP; Var_lnPS_APAP; # slowly perfused:blood

# AS
Var_PK_AS; Var_lnPK_AS;
Var_PF_AS; Var_lnPF_AS;
Var_PL_AS; Var_lnPL_AS;
Var_PG_AS; Var_lnPG_AS;
Var_PM_AS; Var_lnPM_AS;
Var_PR_AS; Var_lnPR_AS;
Var_PS_AS; Var_lnPS_AS;

# AG
Var_PK_AG; Var_lnPK_AG;
Var_PF_AG; Var_lnPF_AG;
Var_PL_AG; Var_lnPL_AG;
Var_PG_AG; Var_lnPG_AG;
Var_PM_AG; Var_lnPM_AG;
Var_PR_AG; Var_lnPR_AG;
Var_PS_AG; Var_lnPS_AG;

```

```

# Biochemical Parameters
#-----

# PAPS second order rate constant
#-----
Var_kPAPS; Var_lnkPAPS;
Var_kPAPS_syn; Var_lnkPAPS_syn;

# GA second order rate constant
#-----
Var_kGA; Var_lnkGA;
Var_kGA_syn; Var_lnkGA_syn;

#CYP Oxidase Params (Liver)
#-----
Var_CYP_Km; Var_lnCYP_Km;
Var_CYP_VmaxC; Var_lnCYP_VmaxC;

# Glucoronidation (Liver)
#-----
Var_UGT_Km; Var_lnUGT_Km;           # Km for entire UGT 2
Var_UGT_VmaxC; Var_lnUGT_VmaxC;    # Vmax in Liver
Var_UGT_Km_GA; Var_lnUGT_Km_GA;
Var_UGT_Ki;   Var_lnUGT_Ki;
Var_Vmax_AG; Var_lnVmax_AG;
Var_Km_AG;   Var_lnKm_AG;

# Sulfation by PAPS (Liver)
#-----
Var_SULT_KVar_apap; Var_lnSULT_Km_apap;
Var_SULT_KVar_paps; Var_lnSULT_Km_paps;
Var_SULT_Ki;   Var_lnSULT_Ki;
Var_SULT_VmaxC; Var_lnSULT_VmaxC; # Vmax in Liver
Var_Vmax_AS;  Var_lnVmax_AS;
Var_Km_AS;    Var_lnKm_AS;
#endregion

#endregion

#-----
#                               Data Error (Verr_...)
#-----
#region
# Needed if you are using an error distribution, rather than error at specific time points.

Verr_CPL_APAP_mcmolL; Verr_CPL_APAP_mcgL;
Verr_CPL_AG_mcmolL;  Verr_CPL_AG_mcgL;
Verr_CPL_AS_mcmolL; Verr_CPL_AS_mcgL;

Verr_lnCPL_APAP_mcmolL_samp; Verr_lnCPL_APAP_mcgL_samp;
Verr_lnCPL_AG_mcmolL_samp;  Verr_lnCPL_AG_mcgL_samp;
Verr_lnCPL_AS_mcmolL_samp;  Verr_lnCPL_AS_mcgL_samp;

Verr_CU_APAP_mcg;
Verr_CU_AG_mcg;
Verr_CU_AS_mcg;

Verr_lnCU_APAP_mcg_samp;
Verr_lnCU_AG_mcg_samp;
Verr_lnCU_AS_mcg_samp;

#endregion

#-----
#                               State Variables (Dependent Variables in ODE)
#-----
#region

States = {
#=====
# Meabolism Rates
#=====
# Liver
#-----
# CYP           # Sulfation           # Glucoronidation
CL_APAP_to_NAPQI_CYP, CL_APAP_to_AS_SULT, CL_APAP_to_AG_UGT,

#=====
# Chemical Amounts (micromol)
#=====
# Stomach
AST_Oral_APAP, AST_APAP, AST_to_Gut_APAP,

# Adipose   # Rapid   # Slow
AF_APAP,   AR_APAP, AS_APAP,
AF_AS,     AR_AS,   AS_AS,
AF_AG,     AR_AG,   AS_AG,

```

```

# Kidney
AKE_APAP, AKE_AS, AKE_AG,
AK_APAP, AK_AS, AK_AG,
# Liver
AL_APAP, AL_AS, AL_AG, AL_PAPS, AL_GA, CH_AG, CH_AG_to_CL_AG, CH_AS, CH_AS_to_CL_AS,

# Muscle
AM_APAP, AM_AS, AM_AG,

# Blood      Arterial
              ABLA_APAP, ABLA_AS, ABLA_AG,
#            Venous
ABL_IV_APAP, ABLV_APAP, ABLV_AS, ABLV_AG,

# Urine
AU_APAP, AU_AS, AU_AG, pct_abs

# Inactive Cofactor
#AL_PAPS_inact, AL_GA_inact

};
#endregion

#-----
#                               Inputs (Switches for Exposures)
#-----
#region

Inputs = {
# ORAL EXPOSURE
#-----
OralExp_APAP, IVEExp_APAP
};

#endregion

#-----
#                               Outputs from the Model
#-----
#region
Outputs = {
# Anything in CalcOutputs must go here

CF_APAP, CK_APAP, CL_APAP, CR_APAP, CS_APAP,

CF_AS, CK_AS, CL_AS, CR_AS, CS_AS,

CF_AG, CK_AG, CL_AG, CR_AG, CS_AG,

CA_APAP, CV_APAP, CPL_APAP,

CA_AS, CV_AS, CPL_AS,

CA_AG, CV_AG, CPL_AG,

CPL_APAP_mcmolL, CPL_APAP_mcgL, CPL_AG_mcmolL,
CPL_AG_mcgL, CPL_AS_mcmolL, CPL_AS_mcgL,
CL_APAP_mcmolL, CL_APAP_mcgL,
CU_APAP_mcg, CU_AG_mcg, CU_AS_mcg,
f_abs,

lnCPL_APAP_mcgL, lnCPL_AG_mcgL, lnCPL_AS_mcgL,
lnCU_APAP_mcg, lnCU_AG_mcg, lnCU_AS_mcg,
lnf_abs,

Verr_lnCPL_APAP_mcmolL, Verr_lnCPL_APAP_mcgL,
Verr_lnCPL_AG_mcmolL, Verr_lnCPL_AG_mcgL,
Verr_lnCPL_AS_mcmolL, Verr_lnCPL_AS_mcgL,

Verr_lnCU_APAP_mcg,
Verr_lnCU_AG_mcg,
Verr_lnCU_AS_mcg

};

#endregion

#-----
#                               Initialize the Model
#-----
#region

Initialize {

# Rescale log-transformed params
#-----
#region
# Rescale the log transformed params here, comment out if no log re-scale needed

#fa = exp(lnfa);

```

```

BW = exp(lnBW);

QCC = exp(lnQCC);
VFC = exp(lnVFC);
VKC = exp(lnVKC);
VGC = exp(lnVGC);
VLC = exp(lnVLC);
VMC = exp(lnVMC);
VBLAC = exp(lnVBLAC);
VBLVC = exp(lnVBLVC);
VSC = exp(lnVSC);
VRC = exp(lnVRC);
QFC = exp(lnQFC);
QKC = exp(lnQKC);
QGC = exp(lnQGC);
QLBC = exp(lnQLBC);
QMC = exp(lnQMC);
QSC = exp(lnQSC);
QRC = exp(lnQRC);

# Inital Dosing
#-----
OralDose_APAP_mgkg = exp(lnOralDose_APAP_mgkg);
OralDose_APAP_mg = exp(lnOralDose_APAP_mg);
IVDose_APAP_mgkg = exp(lnIVDose_APAP_mgkg);
IVDose_APAP_mg = exp(lnIVDose_APAP_mg);

# Chemical Specific Transport Params
#-----
kSG_Vm = exp(lnkSG_Vm);      # Kmax for abs to portal
kSG_Km = exp(lnkSG_Km);      # Km for abs to portal
Tg = exp(lnTg);
Tp = exp(lnTp);

CLC_APAP = exp(lnCLC_APAP);  # Total APAP blood clearance (L/hr/kg)
CLC_AS = exp(lnCLC_AS);      # Total AS blood clearance (L/hr/kg)
CLC_AG = exp(lnCLC_AG);      # Total AG blood clearance (L/hr/kg)

BP_APAP = exp(lnBP_APAP);    # Blood:Plasma Ratio
# Rodgers et al.
# APAP
PF_APAP = exp(lnPF_APAP);    # Fat:blood
PG_APAP = exp(lnPG_APAP);    # Gut:blood
PK_APAP = exp(lnPK_APAP);    # Kidney:blood
PL_APAP = exp(lnPL_APAP);    # Liver:blood
PM_APAP = exp(lnPM_APAP);    # Muscle:blood
PR_APAP = exp(lnPR_APAP);    # rapidly perfused:blood
PS_APAP = exp(lnPS_APAP);    # slowly perfused:blood

# AS
PK_AS = exp(lnPK_AS);
PF_AS = exp(lnPF_AS);
PL_AS = exp(lnPL_AS);
PG_AS = exp(lnPG_AS);
PM_AS = exp(lnPM_AS);
PR_AS = exp(lnPR_AS);
PS_AS = exp(lnPS_AS);

# AG
PK_AG = exp(lnPK_AG);
PF_AG = exp(lnPF_AG);
PL_AG = exp(lnPL_AG);
PG_AG = exp(lnPG_AG);
PM_AG = exp(lnPM_AG);
PR_AG = exp(lnPR_AG);
PS_AG = exp(lnPS_AG);

# Biochemical Parameters
#-----

# PAPS second order rate constant
#-----
kPAPS = exp(lnkPAPS);
kPAPS_syn = exp(lnkPAPS_syn);

# GA second order rate constant
#-----
kGA = exp(lnkGA);
kGA_syn = exp(lnkGA_syn);

#CYP Oxidase Params (Liver)
#-----
CYP_Km = exp(lnCYP_Km);
CYP_VmaxC = exp(lnCYP_VmaxC);

# Glucoronidation (Liver) -> GA Cofactor
#-----
UGT_Km = exp(lnUGT_Km);      # Km for entire UGT 2
UGT_VmaxC = exp(lnUGT_VmaxC); # Vmax in Liver
UGT_Km_GA = exp(lnUGT_Km_GA);
UGT_Ki = exp(lnUGT_Ki);

```

```

Vmax_AG = exp(lnVmax_AG);
Km_AG = exp(lnKm_AG);

# Sulfation (Liver) -> PAPS Cofactor
#-----
SULT_Km_apap = exp(lnSULT_Km_apap);
SULT_Km_paps = exp(lnSULT_Km_paps);
SULT_Ki = exp(lnSULT_Ki);
SULT_VmaxC = exp(lnSULT_VmaxC); # Vmax in Liver
Vmax_AS = exp(lnVmax_AS);
Km_AS = exp(lnKm_AS);

#endregion

# APAP oral dose rate (rate of input to stomach (micromol/hr)).
ODose_APAP_mg = (mgkg_flag>0.5 ? OralDose_APAP_mgkg*BW: OralDose_APAP_mg);
fa = (ODose_APAP_mg<1000 ? 0.0005*ODose_APAP_mg + 0.37: 0.88);
ODose_APAP = (fa*ODose_APAP_mg/OralDur_APAP)*(1000./MW_APAP);
true_dose = (fa*ODose_APAP_mg)*(1000./MW_APAP);

# APAP IV dose rate (rate of input to venous blood (micromol/hr)).
IVD_APAP_mg = (mgkg_flag>0.5 ? IVDose_APAP_mgkg*BW: IVDose_APAP_mg);
IVDR_APAP = (IVD_APAP_mg/IVDur_APAP)*(1000./MW_APAP);

#-----
# Specify the compartment volumes (L)
#-----
VTC = VFC+VKC+VGC+VLC+VMC+VBLAC+VBLVC+VRC+VSC;
VF = VFC*BW/VTC; # Fat.
VK = VKC*BW/VTC; # Kidney.
VG = VGC*BW/VTC; # Gut.
VL = VLC*BW/VTC; # Liver.
VM = VMC*BW/VTC; # Muscle.
VBLA = VBLAC*BW/VTC; # Arterial
VBLV = VBLVC*BW/VTC; # Venous
VR = VRC*BW/VTC; # Rapidly Perfused
VS = VSC*BW/VTC; # Slowly Perfused

#-----
# Specify the flow rates (L/hr)
#-----
QTC = QFC+QKC+QGC+QLBC+QMC+QRC+QSC;
QC = QCC*pow(BW,0.75); # Cardiac output (L/hr).

QF = QFC*QC/QTC; # Fat.
QK = QKC*QC/QTC; # Kidney.
QG = QGC*QC/QTC; # Gut.
QM = QMC*QC/QTC; # Gut.
QLB = QLBC*QC/QTC; # Hepatic artery.
QR = QRC*QC/QTC; # Rapidly Perfused
QS = QSC*QC/QTC; # Slowly Perfused
QL = QG+QLB; # Total liver flow.

#-----
# Compute the clearance rates (L/hr)
#-----
CLR_APAP = (alpha_APAP)*CLC_APAP*BW; # Renal clearance (L/hr).
CLR_AS = (alpha_AS)*(CLC_AS)*BW;
CLR_AG = (alpha_AG)*CLC_AG*BW;

#-----
# Compute Allometric Scaling for Vmax
#-----
CYP_Vmax = CYP_VmaxC*pow(BW, 0.75);
UGT_Vmax = UGT_VmaxC*pow(BW, 0.75);
SULT_Vmax = SULT_VmaxC*pow(BW, 0.75);

#-----
# Initialize PAPS and GA at 100% at t=0
#-----
AL_PAPS = 1.;
AL_GA = 1.;

};
#endregion

#-----
# The Model (Actual ODEs)
#-----
#region
Dynamics {

#-----
# Compute the drug tissue/organ concentrations (micromol/L)
#-----
CF_APAP = AF_APAP/VF; # APAP Fat
CVF_APAP = CF_APAP/PF_APAP;
CK_APAP = AK_APAP/VK; # APAP Kidney
CVK_APAP = CK_APAP/PK_APAP;

```

```

CM_APAP = AM_APAP/VM;          # APAP Muscle
CVM_APAP = CM_APAP/PM_APAP;
CL_APAP = AL_APAP/VL;          # APAP Liver
CVL_APAP = CL_APAP/PL_APAP;
CR_APAP = AR_APAP/VR;          # APAP Rapidly Perfused
CVR_APAP = CR_APAP/PR_APAP;
CS_APAP = AS_APAP/VS;          # APAP Slowly Perfused
CVS_APAP = CS_APAP/PS_APAP;

CF_AS = AF_AS/VF;              # AS Fat
CVF_AS = CF_AS/PF_AS;
CK_AS = AK_AS/VK;              # AS Kidney
CVK_AS = CK_AS/PK_AS;
CL_AS = AL_AS/VL;              # AS Liver
CVL_AS = CL_AS/PL_AS;
CM_AS = AM_AS/VM;              # AS Muscle
CVM_AS = CM_AS/PM_AS;
CR_AS = AR_AS/VR;              # AS Rapidly Perfused
CVR_AS = CR_AS/PR_AS;
CS_AS = AS_AS/VS;              # AS Slowly Perfused
CVS_AS = CS_AS/PS_AS;

CF_AG = AF_AG/VF;              # AG Fat
CVF_AG = CF_AG/PF_AG;
CK_AG = AK_AG/VK;              # AG Kidney
CVK_AG = CK_AG/PK_AG;
CL_AG = AL_AG/VL;              # AG Liver
CVL_AG = CL_AG/PL_AG;
CM_AG = AM_AG/VM;              # AG Muscle
CVM_AG = CM_AG/PM_AG;
CR_AG = AR_AG/VR;              # AG Rapidly Perfused
CVR_AG = CR_AG/PR_AG;
CS_AG = AS_AG/VS;              # AG Slowly Perfused
CVS_AG = CS_AG/PS_AG;

#-----
# Compute the blood/plasma concentrations (micromol/L)
#-----
CA_APAP = ABLA_APAP/VBLV;      # APAP Blood
CV_APAP = ABLV_APAP/VBLA;
CPL_APAP = CV_APAP/BP_APAP;

CA_AS = ABLA_AS/VBLA;          # AS Blood
CV_AS = ABLV_AS/VBLV;
CPL_AS = CV_AS/BP_APAP;

CA_AG = ABLA_AG/VBLA;          # AG Blood
CV_AG = ABLV_AG/VBLV;
CPL_AG = CV_AG/BP_APAP;

#=====
# Meabolism Rates
#=====

#-----
# Liver Metabolism (Michaelis-Menten Kinetics)
#-----

dt(CL_APAP_to_NAPQI_CYP) = CYP_Vmax*CL_APAP/(CYP_Km + CL_APAP);
dt(CL_APAP_to_AS_SULT) = SULT_Vmax*(CL_APAP)*(AL_PAPS)/((SULT_Km_apap + CL_APAP +
pow(CL_APAP, 2)/SULT_Ki)*(SULT_Km_paps + AL_PAPS));
dt(CL_APAP_to_AG_UGT) = UGT_Vmax*(CL_APAP)*(AL_GA)/((UGT_Km + CL_APAP +
pow(CL_APAP, 2)/UGT_Ki)*(UGT_Km_GA + AL_GA));

# Cofactor amounts
dt(AL_PAPS) = -dt(CL_APAP_to_AS_SULT) + kPAPS_syn*(1 - AL_PAPS);
dt(AL_GA) = -dt(CL_APAP_to_AG_UGT) + kGA_syn*(1 - AL_GA);

#=====
# Individual Substrate Dynamics
#=====

# APAP
#=====
dt(AST_Oral_APAP) = OralExp_APAP*ODose_APAP;

# Stomach (Dissolution Absorption)
dt(AST_to_Gut_APAP) = true_dose*(exp(-t/Tg)-exp(-t/Tp))/(Tg-Tp);
dt(AST_APAP) = dt(AST_Oral_APAP) - dt(AST_to_Gut_APAP);

# Liver
dt(AL_APAP) = QL*CA_APAP + dt(AST_to_Gut_APAP) - QL*CVL_APAP - dt(CL_APAP_to_NAPQI_CYP) -
dt(CL_APAP_to_AS_SULT) - dt(CL_APAP_to_AG_UGT);
dt(pct_abs) = dt(AST_to_Gut_APAP)/true_dose;

# Venous Blood
dt(ABL_IV_APAP) = IVExp_APAP*IVDR_APAP;
dt(ABLV_APAP) = QF*CVF_APAP + QM*CVM_APAP + QK*CVK_APAP + QL*CVL_APAP +
QR*CVR_APAP + QS*CVS_APAP - QC*CV_APAP + dt(ABL_IV_APAP);

# Arterial Blood

```

```

dt (ABLA_APAP) = QC*(CV_APAP - CA_APAP);

# Fat
dt (AF_APAP) = QF*(CA_APAP - CVF_APAP);

# Muscle
dt (AM_APAP) = QM*(CA_APAP - CVM_APAP);

# Kidney
dt (AKE_APAP) = CLR_APAP*CA_APAP; # APAP Kidney Elimination
dt (AK_APAP) = QK*(CA_APAP - CVK_APAP) - dt (AKE_APAP);

# Rapidly Perfused
dt (AR_APAP) = QR*(CA_APAP - CVR_APAP);

# Slowly Perfused
dt (AS_APAP) = QS*(CA_APAP - CVS_APAP);

# Urine
dt (AU_APAP) = dt (AKE_APAP);

#AS
#==

# liver
dt (CH_AS_to_CL_AS) = Vmax_AS*CH_AS/(Km_AS + CH_AS);
dt (CH_AS) = dt (CL_APAP_to_AS_SULT) - dt (CH_AS_to_CL_AS);
dt (AL_AS) = QL*(CA_AS - CVL_AS) + dt (CH_AS_to_CL_AS);

# fat
dt (AF_AS) = QF*(CA_AS - CVF_AS);

# muscle
dt (AM_AS) = QM*(CA_AS - CVM_AS);

# rapidly perfused
dt (AR_AS) = QR*(CA_AS - CVR_AS);

# slowly perfused
dt (AS_AS) = QS*(CA_AS - CVS_AS);

# venous blood
dt (ABLV_AS) = QK*CVK_AS + QL*CVL_AS + QF*CVF_AS + QM*CVM_AS + QR*CVR_AS + QS*CVS_AS - QC*CV_AS;

# arterial blood
dt (ABLA_AS) = QC*(CV_AS - CA_AS);

# kidney
dt (AKE_AS) = CLR_AS*CA_AS; # AS kidney elimination
dt (AK_AS) = QK*(CA_AS - CVK_AS) - dt (AKE_AS);

# Urine
dt (AU_AS) = dt (AKE_AS);

#AG
#==

# liver
dt (CH_AG_to_CL_AG) = Vmax_AG*CH_AG/(Km_AG + CH_AG);
dt (CH_AG) = dt (CL_APAP_to_AG_UGT) - dt (CH_AG_to_CL_AG);
dt (AL_AG) = QL*(CA_AG - CVL_AG) + dt (CH_AG_to_CL_AG);

# fat
dt (AF_AG) = QF*(CA_AG - CVF_AG);

# fat
dt (AM_AG) = QM*(CA_AG - CVM_AG);

# rapidly perfused
dt (AR_AG) = QR*(CA_AG - CVR_AG);

# slowly perfused
dt (AS_AG) = QS*(CA_AG - CVS_AG);

# venous blood
dt (ABLV_AG) = QK*CVK_AG + QL*CVL_AG + QF*CVF_AG + QM*CVM_AG + QR*CVR_AG + QS*CVS_AG - QC*CV_AG;

# arterial blood
dt (ABLA_AG) = QC*(CV_AG - CA_AG);

# kidney
dt (AKE_AG) = CLR_AG*CA_AG; # AS kidney elimination
dt (AK_AG) = QK*(CA_AG - CVK_AG) - dt (AKE_AG);

# Urine
dt (AU_AG) = dt (AKE_AG);

};
#endregion

```

```

#-----
#                               Calculate the Model Outputs
#-----
#region
CalcOutputs {
CPL_APAP_mcmolL = CPL_APAP; CPL_APAP_mcgL = CPL_APAP*MW_APAP;
CPL_AG_mcmolL = CPL_AG; CPL_AG_mcgL = CPL_AG*MW_AG;
CPL_AS_mcmolL = CPL_AS; CPL_AS_mcgL = CPL_AS*MW_AS;
CL_APAP_mcmolL = CL_APAP; CL_APAP_mcgL = CL_APAP*MW_APAP;

CU_APAP_mcg = AU_APAP*MW_APAP;
CU_AG_mcg = AU_AG*MW_AG;
CU_AS_mcg = AU_AS*MW_AS;
f_abs = AST_to_Gut_APAP/true_dose;

lnCPL_APAP_mcgL = (CPL_APAP_mcgL > 0 ? log(CPL_APAP_mcgL):-20.); # APAP in Plasma
lnCPL_AG_mcgL = (CPL_AG_mcgL > 0 ? log(CPL_AG_mcgL):-20.); # AG in Plasma
lnCPL_AS_mcgL = (CPL_AS_mcgL > 0 ? log(CPL_AS_mcgL):-20.); # AS in Plasma
lnCU_APAP_mcg = (CU_APAP_mcg > 0 ? log(CU_APAP_mcg):-20.); # APAP in Urine
lnCU_AG_mcg = (CU_AG_mcg > 0 ? log(CU_AG_mcg):-20.); # AG in Urine
lnCU_AS_mcg = (CU_AS_mcg > 0 ? log(CU_AS_mcg):-20.); # AS in Urine
lnf_abs = (f_abs > 0 ? log(f_abs): -20);

# Sampled error from measured data points
Verr_lnCPL_APAP_mcmolL=Verr_lnCPL_APAP_mcmolL;
Verr_lnCPL_APAP_mcgL=Verr_lnCPL_APAP_mcgL;
Verr_lnCPL_AG_mcmolL=Verr_lnCPL_AG_mcmolL;
Verr_lnCPL_AG_mcgL=Verr_lnCPL_AG_mcgL;
Verr_lnCPL_AS_mcmolL=Verr_lnCPL_AS_mcmolL;
Verr_lnCPL_AS_mcgL=Verr_lnCPL_AS_mcgL;

Verr_lnCU_APAP_mcg=Verr_lnCU_APAP_mcg;
Verr_lnCU_AG_mcg=Verr_lnCU_AG_mcg;
Verr_lnCU_AS_mcg=Verr_lnCU_AS_mcg;
}

End.

```

Supplementary Text S10. MCSim MCMC script for the acetaminophen PBPK test case.

```

Integrate(Lsodes, 1.0e-5, 3.09e-7, 1);

MCMC("APAP.LTMCMC.out", "", "",
     1, 1000, 4, 1, 1000, 24601);

Level { # Population Level

# Population parameters to be calibrated
# =====
lnTp           = -3.401;
lnCYP_Km       = 4.867;
lnSULT_Ki      = 6.265301;
lnSULT_Km_paps = -0.6931472;
lnUGT_Ki       = 10.9682;
lnUGT_Km_GA    = -0.6931472;

# Original sensitive parameters (15)
Distrib(M_lnTg,          TruncNormal, -1.4552, 0.5, -2.5, 0.0);
Distrib(M_lnCYP_VmaxC,   Uniform,      -2,      5);
Distrib(M_lnSULT_Km_apap, TruncNormal, 5.703, 1, 4.24, 8.0);
Distrib(M_lnSULT_VmaxC,  Uniform,      0,      15);
Distrib(M_lnUGT_Km,      TruncNormal, 8.6995, 1, 7.6009, 9.3926);
Distrib(M_lnUGT_VmaxC,   Uniform,      0,      15);
Distrib(M_lnKm_AG,       TruncNormal, 9.903, 0.3, 8.071, 10.513);
Distrib(M_lnVmax_AG,     Uniform,      7,      15);
Distrib(M_lnKm_AS,       TruncNormal, 10.039, 0.22, 8.974, 10.5427);
Distrib(M_lnVmax_AS,     Uniform,      7,      15);
Distrib(M_lnkGA_syn,     Uniform,      0, 13);
Distrib(M_lnkPAPS_syn,   Uniform,      0, 13);
Distrib(M_lnCLC_APAP,    Uniform,     -6, 1);
Distrib(M_lnCLC_AG,      Uniform,     -6, 1);
Distrib(M_lnCLC_AS,      Uniform,     -6, 1);

# Additional sensitive parameters (5)
Distrib(M_lnQCC,         TruncNormal, 2.785011, 0.4167421, 1.785011, 3.785011)
Distrib(M_lnBP_APAP,     Uniform,     -2.3, 0);
Distrib(M_lnPF_APAP,     TruncNormal, -0.8051967, 0.3923243, -1.805197, 0.1948033);
Distrib(M_lnPL_APAP,     TruncNormal, -0.375421, 0.3996793, -1.375421, 0.624579);
Distrib(M_lnPM_APAP,     TruncNormal, -0.375421, 0.4138126, -1.375421, 0.624579);

# Var
# Original sensitive parameters

```

```

Distrib(Var_lnTg,          InvGamma, 2.25, 0.3125);
Distrib(Var_lnCYP_VmaxC,  InvGamma, 2.25, 0.3125);
Distrib(Var_lnSULT_Km_apap, InvGamma, 2.25, 0.3125);
Distrib(Var_lnSULT_VmaxC,  InvGamma, 2.25, 0.3125);
Distrib(Var_lnUGT_Km,      InvGamma, 2.25, 0.3125);
Distrib(Var_lnUGT_VmaxC,  InvGamma, 2.25, 0.3125);
Distrib(Var_lnKm_AG,       InvGamma, 2.25, 0.3125);
Distrib(Var_lnVmax_AG,     InvGamma, 2.25, 0.3125);
Distrib(Var_lnKm_AS,       InvGamma, 2.25, 0.3125);
Distrib(Var_lnVmax_AS,     InvGamma, 2.25, 0.3125);
Distrib(Var_lnkGA_syn,     InvGamma, 2.25, 0.3125);
Distrib(Var_lnkPAPS_syn,   InvGamma, 2.25, 0.3125);
Distrib(Var_lnCLC_APAP,    InvGamma, 2.25, 0.3125);
Distrib(Var_lnCLC_AG,      InvGamma, 2.25, 0.3125);
Distrib(Var_lnCLC_AS,      InvGamma, 2.25, 0.3125);

# Additional sensitive parameters
Distrib(Var_lnQCC,         InvGamma, 2.25, 0.3125);
Distrib(Var_lnBP_APAP,    InvGamma, 2.25, 0.3125);
Distrib(Var_lnPF_APAP,    InvGamma, 2.25, 0.3125);
Distrib(Var_lnPL_APAP,    InvGamma, 2.25, 0.3125);
Distrib(Var_lnPM_APAP,    InvGamma, 2.25, 0.3125);

# Verr
Distrib(Verr_lnCPL_APAP_mcgL_samp, LogUniform, 0.01, 0.5);
Distrib(Verr_lnCPL_AG_mcgL_samp,   LogUniform, 0.01, 0.5);
Distrib(Verr_lnCPL_AS_mcgL_samp,   LogUniform, 0.01, 0.5);

Likelihood(Data(lnCPL_APAP_mcgL), Normal_v, Prediction(lnCPL_APAP_mcgL), Verr_lnCPL_APAP_mcgL_samp);
Likelihood(Data(lnCPL_AG_mcgL),   Normal_v, Prediction(lnCPL_AG_mcgL),   Verr_lnCPL_AG_mcgL_samp);
Likelihood(Data(lnCPL_AS_mcgL),   Normal_v, Prediction(lnCPL_AS_mcgL),   Verr_lnCPL_AS_mcgL_samp);

Level { # Group Level
# Original sensitive parameters
Distrib(lnTg,          TruncNormal_v, M_lnTg,          Var_lnTg,          -2.5, 0);
Distrib(lnCYP_VmaxC,  TruncNormal_v, M_lnCYP_VmaxC,  Var_lnCYP_VmaxC,  -2.0, 5);
Distrib(lnSULT_Km_apap, TruncNormal_v, M_lnSULT_Km_apap, Var_lnSULT_Km_apap, 4.24, 8);
Distrib(lnSULT_VmaxC, TruncNormal_v, M_lnSULT_VmaxC,  Var_lnSULT_VmaxC,  0, 15);
Distrib(lnUGT_Km,     TruncNormal_v, M_lnUGT_Km,     Var_lnUGT_Km,     7.6009, 9.3926);
Distrib(lnUGT_VmaxC, TruncNormal_v, M_lnUGT_VmaxC,  Var_lnUGT_VmaxC,  0, 15);
Distrib(lnKm_AG,      TruncNormal_v, M_lnKm_AG,      Var_lnKm_AG,      8.071, 10.513);
Distrib(lnVmax_AG,    TruncNormal_v, M_lnVmax_AG,    Var_lnVmax_AG,    7, 15);
Distrib(lnKm_AS,      TruncNormal_v, M_lnKm_AS,      Var_lnKm_AS,      8.974, 10.5427);
Distrib(lnVmax_AS,    TruncNormal_v, M_lnVmax_AS,    Var_lnVmax_AS,    7, 15);
Distrib(lnkGA_syn,    TruncNormal_v, M_lnkGA_syn,    Var_lnkGA_syn,    0, 13);
Distrib(lnkPAPS_syn, TruncNormal_v, M_lnkPAPS_syn,  Var_lnkPAPS_syn,  0, 13);
Distrib(lnCLC_APAP,   TruncNormal_v, M_lnCLC_APAP,   Var_lnCLC_APAP,   -6, 1);
Distrib(lnCLC_AG,     TruncNormal_v, M_lnCLC_AG,     Var_lnCLC_AG,     -6, 1);
Distrib(lnCLC_AS,     TruncNormal_v, M_lnCLC_AS,     Var_lnCLC_AS,     -6, 1);

# Additional sensitive parameters
Distrib(lnQCC,         TruncNormal_v, M_lnQCC,         Var_lnQCC,         1.785011, 3.785011);
Distrib(lnBP_APAP,    TruncNormal_v, M_lnBP_APAP,    Var_lnBP_APAP,    -2.3, 0);
Distrib(lnPF_APAP,    TruncNormal_v, M_lnPF_APAP,    Var_lnPF_APAP,    -1.805197, 0.1948033);
Distrib(lnPL_APAP,    TruncNormal_v, M_lnPL_APAP,    Var_lnPL_APAP,    -1.375421, 0.624579);
Distrib(lnPM_APAP,    TruncNormal_v, M_lnPM_APAP,    Var_lnPM_APAP,    -1.375421, 0.624579);

Level { # Study 1
Simulation { #Volak (2013) 325 mg 9
mgkg_flag = 0;
OralExp_APAP = NDoses(2, 1, 0, 0, 0.001);
OralDose_APAP_mg = 325;
lnOralDose_APAP_mg = 5.78383;
IVExp_APAP = 0.;
IVDose_APAP_mg = 0.;
lnIVDose_APAP_mg = 0.;
BW = 68.;
Print(lnCPL_APAP_mcgL, 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5, 3.0, 4.0, 6.0, 8.0);
Data(lnCPL_APAP_mcgL, 7.5756, 7.8973, 8.0359, 7.9409, 7.7536, 7.5909, 7.3395, 6.6758, 6.1654);
Print(lnCPL_AG_mcgL, 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5, 3.0, 4.0, 6.0, 8.0, 10.0);
Data(lnCPL_AG_mcgL, 5.7038, 7.6639, 8.149, 8.3687, 8.468, 8.5192, 8.4338, 8.052, 7.5549, 7.1624);
Print(lnCPL_AS_mcgL, 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 2.5, 3.0, 4.0, 6.0, 8.0, 10.0);
Data(lnCPL_AS_mcgL, 6.5539, 7.3524, 7.7098, 7.7579, 7.7007, 7.5909, 7.4384, 6.9177, 6.4489, 6.1841);
}
} # End Study 1
Level { # Study 2

```

```

Simulation { # Jensen (2004) 5
mgkg_flag = 0;

OralExp_APAP = NDoses(2, 1, 0, 0, 0.001);
OralDose_APAP_mg = 1000.0;
lnOralDose_APAP_mg = 6.90776;

IVExp_APAP = 0.;
IVDose_APAP_mg = 0.;
lnIVDose_APAP_mg = 0.;

BW = 68.;

# Logged data
Print(lnCPL_APAP_mcgL, 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0, 5.0, 6.0, 8.0);
Data(lnCPL_APAP_mcgL, 9.2797, 9.4681, 9.2923, 9.0719, 8.7246, 8.3994, 8.1881, 7.892, 7.3309);

Print(lnCPL_AG_mcgL, 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0, 5.0, 6.0, 8.0, 10.0);
Data(lnCPL_AG_mcgL, 8.3935, 9.3632, 9.8072, 9.982, 10.0493, 9.926, 9.7817, 9.552, 9.1014, 8.6473);

Print(lnCPL_AS_mcgL, 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0, 5.0, 6.0, 8.0, 10.0);
Data(lnCPL_AS_mcgL, 8.317, 8.7968, 8.9727, 8.887, 8.7968, 8.539, 8.4138, 8.1712, 7.6798, 7.2098);
}
} # End Study 2

Level { # Study 3
Simulation { # Shinoda (2007) 5
mgkg_flag = 0;

OralExp_APAP = NDoses(2, 1, 0, 0, 0.001);
OralDose_APAP_mg = 1000;
lnOralDose_APAP_mg = 6.9077;

IVExp_APAP = 0.;
IVDose_APAP_mg = 0.;
lnIVDose_APAP_mg = 0.;

BW = 60.;

Print(lnCPL_APAP_mcgL, 2.50E-01, 5.00E-01, 7.50E-01, 1.00E+00, 2.00E+00, 3.00E+00, 4.00E+00, 6.00E+00);
Data(lnCPL_APAP_mcgL, 9.6989, 9.7585, 9.6486, 9.5324, 9.2686, 9.0372, 8.8291, 8.4617);

Print(lnCPL_AG_mcgL, 2.50E-01, 5.00E-01, 7.50E-01, 1.00E+00, 2.00E+00, 3.00E+00, 4.00E+00, 6.00E+00);
Data(lnCPL_AG_mcgL, 7.2842, 9.1686, 9.4551, 9.6247, 9.9808, 9.9091, 9.7584, 9.3016);

Print(lnCPL_AS_mcgL, 2.50E-01, 5.00E-01, 7.50E-01, 1.00E+00, 2.00E+00, 3.00E+00, 4.00E+00, 6.00E+00);
Data(lnCPL_AS_mcgL, 7.5479, 8.4928, 8.5595, 8.5595, 8.5884, 8.4446, 8.261, 7.7043);
}
} # End Study 3

Level { # Study 4
Simulation { # Kim (2011) 2
mgkg_flag = 0;

OralExp_APAP = NDoses(2, 1, 0, 0, 0.001);
OralDose_APAP_mg = 1000.;
lnOralDose_APAP_mg = 6.90776;

IVExp_APAP = 0.;
IVDose_APAP_mg = 0.;
lnIVDose_APAP_mg = 0.;

BW = 70.;

Print(lnCPL_APAP_mcgL, 0.25, 0.5, 1, 1.5, 2, 3, 4, 6, 8);
Data(lnCPL_APAP_mcgL, 8.3405, 8.0456, 8.5271, 9.0607, 9.0927, 9.0466, 8.8393, 8.2188, 7.5704);

Print(lnCPL_AG_mcgL, 0.25, 0.5, 1, 1.5, 2, 3, 4, 6, 8, 10);
Data(lnCPL_AG_mcgL, 6.2383, 6.9276, 8.1831, 8.7749, 9.1485, 9.5819, 9.705, 9.5956, 9.1788, 8.6945);

Print(lnCPL_AS_mcgL, 0.25, 0.5, 1, 1.5, 2, 3, 4, 6, 8, 10);
Data(lnCPL_AS_mcgL, 6.2383, 6.5482, 7.6917, 8.1577, 8.3939, 8.5773, 8.5679, 8.2242, 7.7187, 7.2226);
}
} # End Study 4

Level { # Study 5
Simulation { # Prescott1 3 (1980)
mgkg_flag = 1;

OralExp_APAP = NDoses(2, 1, 0, 0, 0.001);
OralDose_APAP_mgkg = 20.0;
lnOralDose_APAP_mgkg = 2.99573;

IVExp_APAP = 0.;
IVDose_APAP_mgkg = 0.;
lnIVDose_APAP_mgkg = 0.;

BW = 72.;

# Logged
Print(lnCPL_APAP_mcgL, 0.25, 0.5, 0.75, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0, 6.0, 8.0);
Data(lnCPL_APAP_mcgL, 9.6486, 9.8363, 9.8416, 9.7981, 9.655, 9.5178, 9.2203, 8.9187, 8.294, 7.836);

Print(lnCPL_AG_mcgL, 0.25, 0.5, 0.75, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0, 6.0, 8.0);
Data(lnCPL_AG_mcgL, 8.0722, 8.9804, 9.5047, 9.806, 10.1138, 10.2139, 10.1567, 10.0871, 9.6304, 9.2425);
}
}

```

```

Print(lnCPL_AS_mcgL, 0.25, 0.5, 0.75, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0, 6.0, 8.0);
Data(lnCPL_AS_mcgL, 8.1743, 8.8166, 9.0136, 9.1653, 9.1427, 9.0802, 8.9097, 8.8052, 8.394, 7.9587);
}
} # End Study 5

Level { # Study 6
Simulation { #Chan (1997) 3

mgkg_flag = 1;

OralExp_APAP = NDoses(2, 1, 0, 0, 0.001);
OralDose_APAP_mgkg = 20.0;
lnOralDose_APAP_mgkg = 2.99573;

IVExp_APAP = 0.;
IVDose_APAP_mgkg = 0.;
lnIVDose_APAP_mgkg = 0.;

BW = 57.;

Print(lnCPL_APAP_mcgL, 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0, 5.0, 6.0, 7.0, 8.0);
Data(lnCPL_APAP_mcgL, 9.9184, 9.8934, 9.8092, 9.6486, 9.3147, 9.0131, 8.7323, 8.4949, 8.1719, 8.0678);

Print(lnCPL_AG_mcgL, 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0, 5.0, 6.0, 7.0, 8.0);
Data(lnCPL_AG_mcgL, 8.8496, 9.6346, 9.9605, 10.0689, 10.0689, 9.9585, 9.8012, 9.6501, 9.4602, 9.3075);

Print(lnCPL_AS_mcgL, 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0, 5.0, 6.0, 7.0, 8.0);
Data(lnCPL_AS_mcgL, 8.5855, 8.9833, 9.1311, 9.1195, 8.9737, 8.8098, 8.6137, 8.4609, 8.253, 8.0158);
}
} # End Study 6

Level { # Study 7
Simulation { # Critchley et al. (2005) Grace 1

mgkg_flag = 1;

OralExp_APAP = NDoses(2, 1, 0, 0, 0.001);
OralDose_APAP_mgkg = 20.0;
lnOralDose_APAP_mgkg = 2.99573;

IVExp_APAP = 0.;
IVDose_APAP_mgkg = 0.;
lnIVDose_APAP_mgkg = 0.;

BW = 57;

Print(lnCPL_APAP_mcgL, 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0, 5.0, 6.0, 7.0, 8.0);
Data(lnCPL_APAP_mcgL, 9.9942, 9.8147, 9.6291, 9.488, 9.2496, 8.9708, 8.6604, 8.3825, 8.197, 7.9374);

Print(lnCPL_AG_mcgL, 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0, 5.0, 6.0, 7.0, 8.0, 9.0, 10.0);
Data(lnCPL_AG_mcgL, 8.3168, 9.4047, 9.6884, 9.8343, 9.8896, 9.8319, 9.6924, 9.5144, 9.2735, 9.0257, 8.8558,
8.7345);

Print(lnCPL_AS_mcgL, 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0, 5.0, 6.0, 7.0, 8.0, 9.0, 10.0);
Data(lnCPL_AS_mcgL, 8.4314, 8.9362, 9.0191, 8.9872, 8.9158, 8.7388, 8.5682, 8.3765, 8.204, 7.964, 7.7515, 7.5234);
}
} # End Study 7

Level { # Study 8
Simulation { # Chiew1 1 (2010)

mgkg_flag = 1.;

OralExp_APAP = NDoses(2, 1, 0, 0, 0.001);
OralDose_APAP_mgkg = 79.;
lnOralDose_APAP_mgkg = 4.3694;

IVExp_APAP = 0.;
IVDose_APAP_mgkg = 0.;
lnIVDose_APAP_mgkg = 0.;

BW = 73.11;

Print(lnCPL_APAP_mcgL, 0.5, 0.75, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0, 6.0, 8.0);
Data(lnCPL_APAP_mcgL, 11.1496, 11.357, 11.1583, 10.9794, 10.9794, 10.8735, 10.6532, 10.1775, 9.6145);

Print(lnCPL_AG_mcgL, 0.5, 0.75, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0, 6.0, 8.0, 10.0, 12.0);
Data(lnCPL_AG_mcgL, 9.3288, 10.1109, 10.5093, 11.0057, 11.2879, 11.5434, 11.5929, 11.4362, 11.0941, 10.7324,
10.3191);

Print(lnCPL_AS_mcgL, 0.5, 0.75, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0, 3.0, 4.0, 6.0, 8.0, 10.0, 12.0);
Data(lnCPL_AS_mcgL, 8.6702, 9.1882, 9.3634, 9.577, 9.7297, 9.8477, 9.9619, 9.8872, 9.689, 9.4287, 9.0757);
}
} # End Study 8

} # Group
} # Population

End.

```


Supplementary Figure S1. Marginal posterior distributions of the sampled slope a in the linear regression model, at different perk values.

Supplementary Figure S2. Marginal posterior distributions of the sampled SD σ_1 in the linear regression model, at different perk values.

Supplementary Figure S3. Marginal posterior distributions of the sampled SD σ_2 in the linear regression model, at different perk values.

Supplementary Figure S4. Plots of the probability density functions of the prior and exact posterior distributions of the estimated mean in the Gaussian inference problem.

Supplementary Figure S5. Perks values sampled as a function of the tempered TI MCMC sampler iteration, in the case of the acetaminophen population PBPK model.

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